

Supplement to the Staphylinidae fauna of Crete and the Aegean
Islands, Greece (Coleoptera)

With 71 figures and 3 tables

VOLKER ASSING †

† Volker Assing died completely unforeseen after sending the last corrections to this article. Unfortunately, he was no longer able to confirm their implementation. The editorial team hopes to have implemented everything in his will. We mourn the loss of an outstanding taxonomist and esteemed colleague.

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Abstract

Recent field trips to Crete, Samos, and Rhodos, as well as a revision of other material from various collections yielded numerous additional records, species, and taxonomic changes for the Staphylinidae faunas of Crete and the Aegean Islands. Fifteen species are described and illustrated for the first time, two of the Pselaphinae, two of the Oxytelinae, two of the Aleocharinae, one of the Leptotyphlinae, and eight of the Scydmaeninae: *Paramaurops creticus* BRACHAT spec. nov. (Crete: Psiloritis range); *Afropselaphus chanianus* BRACHAT spec. nov. (Crete); *Euphania ambulans* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *Bledius (Hesperophilus) bedelianus* SCHÜLKE spec. nov. (Samos, Rhodos, Karpathos, South Turkey, Lebanon, Israel); *Hydrosmecta cultellata* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *Atheta (Philhygra) tecta* ASSING spec. nov. (Samo-thraki, Samos, Kos, Turkey); *Cretotyphlus kerkisicus* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *Cephennium amplexans* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *C. monstrans* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *C. icariae* ASSING spec. nov. (Ikaría); *C. rhodicum* ASSING spec. nov. (Rhodos); *Stenichnus (Stenichnus) samius* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Samos); *S. (S.) amphimykalicus* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Samos, Southwest Turkey); *Scydmorephes amphimykalicus* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Samos, Southwest Turkey); *Euconnus (Tetramelus) rhodicus* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Rhodos). Three new synonymies are proposed: *Throbalium cycladicum* (KOCH, 1937) = *T. biblicum* (KOCH, 1937), syn. nov., = *T. adanense* KOCH, 1939, syn. nov., = *Throbalium kosianum* BORDONI, 2020, syn. nov. Two new combinations are proposed: *Tychus kerkisicus* (BRACHAT, 2017), comb. nov. (ex *Paratychnus* BESUCHET, 1960) and *Liogluta aloconotoides* (BENICK, 1940), comb. nov. (ex *Alocnota* THOMSON, 1858). Several previous misidentifications are rectified. Numerous species are reported from Crete and the Aegean Islands for the first time, some even from Greece and from Europe. New checklists of the Staphylinidae of Samos and Rhodos are provided. Including the additions and changes, the faunas of Crete, Samos, and Rhodos are now represented by 403 identified named species (114 of them endemic), 199 named species (15 endemic), and 160 named species (10 endemic), respectively.

Taxonomic acts

Paramaurops creticus BRACHAT spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:0ADD6720-1EEC-4E67-90EE-F1DC5B1C9ACE
Afropselaphus chanianus BRACHAT spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7648FB38-4026-414C-8609-32447D514299
Euphania ambulans ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:4D363881-A549-4AA0-A824-66E2EBA02BD3
Bledius bedelianus SCHÜLKE spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:84848C14-D6BD-41DF-9D76-EFDDC83FE7CD
Hydrosmecta cultellata ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:014960F5-7A69-4D33-8B6F-2F543D07AF7D

- Atheta tecta* ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2794087C-8BD2-4278-A358-D0CE8A62C1DB
Cretotyphlus kerkisicus ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:16BD4F7A-B7A6-47B3-8025-342CAD1855EF
Cephennium amplexans ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:41A5DF62-9FFC-44D3-A57C-20B2B93720B9
Cephennium monstrans ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:86CB13EF-3F05-45A1-BB47-034707B226A5
Cephennium icariae ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:738FF668-DCED-4E48-808C-0DE0D67797CA
Cephennium rhodicum ASSING spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:63142283-CD20-46E9-AB60-9F7AFA6DE29A
Stenichnus samius MEYBOHM spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:D281CE0D-EEA6-45E7-BCB2-21734004DD80
Stenichnus amphimykalicus MEYBOHM spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:BC1B8722-6DC0-40C0-BC10-9A2E-673C9E4E
Scydmorephes amphimykalicus MEYBOHM spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2CDA0C85-BA74-46EF-8AA6-ADAFB1974DC2
Euconnus rhodicus MEYBOHM spec. nov. – urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:A286F3E4-9AC8-434F-B473-96E388B238A8

Key words

Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Palaearctic region, East Mediterranean, Greece, Crete, Aegean Islands, taxonomy, endemism, endogean fauna, new species, new synonymies, new combinations, additional records, checklists

Zusammenfassung

In den letzten Jahren durchgeführte Forschungsreisen nach Kreta, Samos und Rhodos sowie eine Revision von weiterem Material aus mehreren Sammlungen ergaben zahlreiche weitere Nachweise, Arten und taxonomische Änderungen für die Staphylinidenfauna Kretas und der ägäischen Inseln. Fünfzehn Arten aus den Unterfamilien Pselaphinae (2 Arten), Oxytelinae (2), Aleocharinae (2), Leptotyphlinae (1) und Scydmaeninae (8) werden erstmals beschrieben und abgebildet: *Paramaurops creticus* BRACHAT spec. nov. (Kreta: Psiloritis); *Afropselaphus chanianus* BRACHAT spec. nov. (Kreta); *Euphantias ambulans* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *Bledius (Hesperophilus) bedelianus* SCHÜLKE spec. nov. (Samos, Rhodos, Karpathos, Südtürkei, Libanon, Israel); *Hydrosmecta cultellata* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *Atheta (Phillygra) tecta* ASSING spec. nov. (Samothraki, Samos, Kos, Türkei); *Cretotyphlus kerkisicus* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *Cephennium amplexans* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *C. monstrans* ASSING spec. nov. (Samos); *C. icariae* ASSING spec. nov. (Ikaria); *C. rhodicum* ASSING spec. nov. (Rhodos); *Stenichnus (Stenichnus) samius* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Samos); *S. (S.) amphimykalicus* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Samos, Südwesttürkei); *Scydmorephes amphimykalicus* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Samos, Südwesttürkei); *Euconnus (Tetramelus) rhodicus* MEYBOHM spec. nov. (Rhodos). Drei Namen werden synonymisiert: *Throbalium cycladicum* (KOCH, 1937) = *T. biblicum* (KOCH, 1937), syn. nov., = *T. adanense* KOCH, 1939, syn. nov., = *Throbalium kosianum* BORDONI, 2020, syn. nov. Zwei Arten werden in andere Gattungen transferiert: *Tychus kerkisicus* (BRACHAT, 2017), comb. nov. (ex *Paratychnus* BESUCHET, 1960) und *Liogluta aloconotooides* (BENICK, 1940), comb. nov. (ex *Aloconota* THOMSON, 1858). Einige auf Fehldetermination beruhende frühere Nachweise werden korrigiert. Zahlreiche Arten werden erstmals von Kreta und den ägäischen Inseln nachgewiesen, darunter auch eine Reihe von Erstnachweisen für Griechenland und sogar für Europa. Für Samos und Rhodos werden neue Checklisten erstellt. Einschließlich der Ergänzungen und taxonomischen Änderungen sind derzeit von Kreta 403 benannte (und identifizierte) Arten (davon 114 endemisch), von Samos 199 benannte Arten (15 davon endemisch) und von Rhodos 160 benannte Arten (10 davon endemisch) bekannt.

Schlüsselwörter

Coleoptera, Staphylinidae, Paläarktis, Ostmediterraneis, Griechenland, Kreta, Ägäische Inseln, Taxonomie, Endemismus, endogäische Fauna, Beschreibungen, neue Arten, neue Synonymien, weitere Nachweise

Introduction

The Staphylinidae of the Greek islands had received relatively little attention until little more than a decade ago, although, in view of the geographic, geological, and climatic history and conditions, many of them could be expected to host endemic species. In the past years, however, numerous articles have been published addressing the faunas particularly of Crete (see ASSING

2019c, ASSING et al. 2019, and references cited therein), Karpathos (ASSING 2016a), and the eastern Aegean islands (only the respective latest contributions cited): Samothraki (ASSING 2019b), Lesbos (ASSING 2016b), Chios (ASSING 2015b), Samos (ASSING 2017b), Ikaria (2017b), and Rhodos (ASSING 2013). While the first visits to these islands focused on the epigeic fauna, a

survey of the endogean species began in 2018 in Crete (ASSING 2018d, ASSING 2019c, ASSING et al. 2019) and continued in Samothraki (ASSING 2019b). Since then, two field trips have been conducted to Crete and Samos, again mainly targeting the endogean fauna, the former conducted by the author in December 2019 and the latter in cooperation with Volker Brachat (Geretsried) and Thomas Forcke (Hannover) in April 2022. Moreover, Thomas Forcke conducted a field trip to Rhodos from the end of December to the beginning of January, primarily aiming at studying Carabidae, but also collecting Staphylinidae.

Additional changes to the faunas of the islands have been brought about by several generic revisions, other taxonomic studies, and faunistic contributions. In consequence, the previously published species inventories are now more or less outdated, particularly those of Samos and Rhodos, for which updated checklists are provided in this paper. Also, various previously unnamed, mostly endemic species are described, partly by Volker Brachat and Heinrich Meybohm (Großhansdorf). Descriptions of Pselaphinae are exclusively authored by Volker Brachat, those of Scydmaeninae, except *Cephennium* MÜLLER & KUNZE, 1822, by Heinrich Meybohm, and one of a more widespread species of *Bledius* LEACH, 1819 by Michael Schülke (Berlin). The remaining new species are described by the author.

Material and methods

The material treated in this study is deposited in the following public and private collections:

IRSNB	Institut Royal des Sciences Naturelles de Belgique, Bruxelles (Y. Gérard)
MHNG	Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle, Genève (G. Cuccodoro)
MNB	Museum für Naturkunde Berlin (incl. coll. Schülke)
NHMB	Naturhistorisches Museum Basel (M. Borer, I. Zürcher)
NHMW	Naturhistorisches Museum Wien (H. Schillhammer)
SDEI	Senckenberg Deutsches Entomologisches Institut, Müncheberg (M. Schröter)
cAss	private collection Volker Assing, Hannover
cBra	private collection Volker Brachat, Geretsried
cDeg	private collection Gregor Degasperi, Innsbruck
cFel	private collection Benedikt Feldmann, Münster
cKle	private collection Andreas Kleeberg, Berlin
cMey	private collection Heinrich Meybohm, Großhansdorf

For the morphological studies conducted by the author, a Stemi SV 11 microscope (Zeiss), a Discovery V12 microscope (Zeiss), and a Jenalab compound microscope (Carl Zeiss Jena) were used. The images were created using

digital cameras (Nikon Coolpix 995, Axiocam ERc 5s), as well as Labscope and Picolay stacking software.

Measurements: body length was measured from the anterior margin of the mandibles (in resting position) or the labrum (whichever forms the anterior apex of the head) to the posterior apex of the elytra (Scydmaeninae) or to the abdominal apex (other subfamilies), the length of the forebody from the apex of the head to the posterior margin of the elytra (all subfamilies except Scydmaeninae), head length along the middle from the anterior margin of the clypeus (without ante-clypeus) (Aleocharinae) or the anterior margin of the frons (other subfamilies) to the posterior constriction of the head, head width across (and including) eyes, elytral length at the suture from the apex of the scutellum to the posterior margin of the elytra (except in *Bledius*), and the length of (the median lobe of) the aedeagus from the apex of the ventral process to the base of the aedeagal capsule unless stated otherwise. The “parameral” side (i.e., the side where the sperm duct enters) is referred to as the ventral, the opposite side as the dorsal aspect.

The Staphylinidae fauna of Crete

The fauna of Crete is remarkable not only regarding its diversity (397 named species prior to this study), but also with respect to the number of endemic species (111 named), many of them locally endemic. A comprehensive overview of the Staphylinidae of Crete was provided in a recent two-part monograph (ASSING 2019, ASSING et al. 2019). In the meantime an additional field trip was conducted to this island by the author in December 2019, with a special focus on the endogean fauna. Compared to previous field trips to Crete, the 2019 results were relatively poor, yielding a total of only 294 specimens, with merely two new species of Pselaphinae, a first record of a species of Tachyporinae, and few additional records of other species (Tab. 1). Moreover, two additional species, *Carpelimus gusarovi* GILDENKOV, 1992 and *C. exiguus* (ERICHSON, 1839), were reported from Crete for the first time by GILDENKOV & MANTIČ (2020). According to SCHÜLKE (2019), there is evidence that *Planeustomus elegantulus* (KRAATZ, 1857) is endemic to Crete. Andreas Kleeberg (pers. comm.) communicated the first record of *Ochtheophilus andalusiacus* (FAGEL, 1957) from the island (see details below). Including the new species and the additional records, 403 named species are currently known from Crete, with 114 (28.2 %) of them endemic.

Localities/samples: December 2019, leg. Assing: **1:** SW Chania, WSW Lakki, 35°23'53"N, 23°54'38"E, 390 m, stream valley, very old chestnut on slope near road, stony soil with little humus, soil washing, 21.XII.2019; **1a:** SW Chania, WSW Lakki, 35°23'53"N, 23°54'38"E, 390 m, stream valley, beneath *Platanus orientalis* near stream, fine soil with humus,

Tab. 1: Staphylinidae recorded from Crete in December 2019. Details on the localities/samples are provided at the end of the list. Specimen numbers are given in parentheses behind the sample number. First records from Crete are marked with an asterisk, endemics are preceded by a “+”.

Species	Localities/samples
O m a l i i n a e	
+ <i>Boreaphilus fuelscheri</i> ZERCHE, 1990	24(1), 29(1)
P r o t e i n i n a e	
+ <i>Proteinus creticus</i> ASSING, 2004	19a(1)
P s e l a p h i n a e	
+* <i>Afropselaphus chanianus</i> BRACHAT, spec. nov.	1(1)
+ <i>Bryaxis meybohmianus</i> BRACHAT, 2019	1(5), 4(1), 5(2), 5(2), 8(1), 9(3), 18(2)
+ <i>Euplectus assingi</i> BRACHAT, 2019	1(1), 18(1)
+* <i>Paramaurops creticus</i> BRACHAT, spec. nov.	19a(1)
+ <i>Tychus reitterianus</i> LÖBL, 1998	7(2), 11(2), 12(1)
T a c h y p o r i n a e	
* <i>Lordithon trinotatus</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)	41a(1), 96a(1), 159(1), 172(1), 193(1), 212(1)
<i>Mycetoporus ignidorsum</i> EPPELSHEIM, 1880	21a(1)
<i>Tachyporus caucasicus</i> (KOLENATI, 1846)	17(1), 19a(1)
H a b r o c e r i n a e	
<i>Habrocerus pisidicus</i> KORGE, 1971	7(11), 15(1), 19a(26)
A l e o c h a r i n a e	
+ <i>Alevonota cretica</i> ASSING & WUNDERLE, 2008	29(1)
<i>Aloconota subgrandis</i> (BRUNDIN, 1954)	7(1), 27(3)
<i>Atheta aeneicollis</i> (SHARP, 1869)	1(2), 1a(1), 6(1), 12(1), 13(1), 15(1), 20(1)
+ <i>Atheta cretica</i> BRUNDIN, 1944	7(1), 13(2)
<i>Atheta (Mocyta) spp.</i>	1(1), 15(1), 19a(2)
+ <i>Bellatheta albimontis</i> ASSING, 2015	2(1)
<i>Bolitochara obliqua</i> ERICHSON, 1837	14a(4)
<i>Cousya defecta</i> (MULSANT & REY, 1875)	14a(1)
+ <i>Geostiba meybohmi</i> ASSING, 2000	21a(3), 22(24), 24(1), 29(5), 30(2)
<i>Geostiba oertzeni</i> (EPPELSHEIM, 1888)	2(14), 3(4), 5(3), 6(2), 15(3), 16(4), 17(1), 27(6), 28(2), 29(4)
<i>Myllaena intermedia</i> ERICHSON, 1837	7(36)
<i>Oxypoda flavicornis</i> KRAATZ, 1856	29(4)
<i>Oxypoda rectacia</i> ASSING, 2019	7(1), 10(1), 19a(3)
O x y t e l i n a e	
<i>Anotylus tetracaratus</i> (BLOCK, 1799)	26(1)
<i>Carpelimus corticinus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)	7(10)
<i>Platystethus nitens</i> (C.R. SAHLBERG, 1832)	19a(1)
S t e n i n a e	
<i>Stenus ochropus</i> KIESENWETTER, 1858	21a(2)
S c y d m a e n i n a e	
+ <i>Cephennium idanum</i> ASSING, 2019	22(2), 25(2)
<i>Cephennium spp. (♀)</i>	28(1), 29(1)
+ <i>Scydmorephes zieglerei</i> MEYBOHM, 2008	26(1), 28(2), 29(3)
+ <i>Stenichnus brachati</i> MEYBOHM, 2019	21a(2)

Species	Localities/samples
L e p t o t y p h l i n a e	
+ <i>Allotyphlus foedatus</i> ASSING, 2019	1(1), 1a(2), 3(2), 5(1), 12(1), 16(2), 19(1)
+ <i>Cretotyphlus idanus</i> ASSING, 2019	19(1)
+ <i>Kenotyphlus virgatus</i> ASSING, 2019	6(2)
P a e d e r i n a e	
+ <i>Leptobium creticum</i> COIFFAIT, 1973	5(1), 15(1), 23(1)
+ <i>Medon cerrutii</i> COIFFAIT, 1976	6(2), 7(1), 15(1)
<i>Medon dilutus pythonissa</i> (SAULCY, 1865)	7(1), 12(1), 13(1), 15(2), 18(1)
<i>Sunius fallax</i> (LOKAY, 1919)	7(3)
S t a p h y l i n i n a e	
<i>Gyrohypnus angustatus</i> STEPHENS, 1833	7(1)
<i>Ocypus mus</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	20(1)
<i>Othius lapidicola</i> MÄRKEL & KIESENWETTER, 1848	18(1), 23(2), 24(1), 25(2), 30(1)
<i>Quedius nemoralis</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1848	22(1)
+ <i>Quedius sigwalti</i> COIFFAIT, 1972	7(2), 19a(1)
+ <i>Xantholinus creticus</i> ASSING, 2006	24(2)

soil washing, 21.XII.2019; **2**: SW Chania, WSW Lakki, 35°23'53"N, 23°54'38"E, 390 m, stream valley, beneath *Platanus orientalis* near stream, soil washing, 22.XII.2019; **3**: SW Chania, W Omalos Plateau, 35°21'11"N, 23°48'42"E, 790 m, dry stream valley with old *Platanus orientalis* on slope with *Juniperus* and phrygana, soil washing beneath *Platanus* and between rocks, 21.XII.2019; **4**: SW Chania, W Omalos Plateau, 35°20'50"N, 23°49'20"E, 710 m, moist slope with chestnut, soil washing, 21.XII.2019; **5**: SW Chania, W Omalos Plateau, 35°20'21"N, 23°49'50"E, 640 m, ruderal slope with *Quercus ilex* and bushes, soil washing near dry stream bed, 21.XII.2019; **6**: S Kissamos, Mili, 35°23'18"N, 23°39'49"E, 350 m, stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing near stream, 22.XII.2019; **7**: S Kissamos, Limni, 35°22'15"N, 23°37'55"E, 570 m, margin of artificial pond with old *Platanus orientalis*, litter sifted, 22.XII.2019; **8**: NE Kandalos, Spina, 35°21'43"N, 23°46'51"E, 710 m, stream valley with oak, *Platanus orientalis*, other trees, and fern undergrowth, soil washing, 22.XII.2019; **9**: NE Kandalos, Spina, 35°21'46"N, 23°46'38"E, 700 m, moist slope with very old chestnut, soil washing, 22.XII.2019; **10**: SE Chania, SW Melidoni, 35°20'44"N, 24°05'49"E, 1030 m, stony slope with *Cedrus* and *Quercus ilex*, soil washing, 23.XII.2019; **11**: SE Chania, W Melidoni, 35°23'35"N, 24°05'45"E, 400 m, small dry stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing, 23.XII.2019; **12**: SE Chania, Ramni, 35°23'51"N, 24°05'56"E, 400 m, grassy slope with old oak and *Rubus* undergrowth, sandy soil washing, 23.XII.2019; **13**: SE Chania, Kambi, 35°24'57"N, 24°04'09"E, 550 m, ruderal slope with old oak, soil washing, 23.XII.2019; **14**: SW Chania, S Nteres, 35°24'48"N, 23°50'46"E, 290 m, stream valley

with very old chestnut trees, soil washing (stony soil), 24.XII.2019; **14a**: same data, but litter sifted; **15**: SW Chania, S Nteres, 35°24'15"N, 23°50'58"E, 320 m, stream valley with chestnut trees, soil washing (stony soil), 24.XII.2019; **16**: SW Chania, N Nteres, 35°27'40"N, 23°50'18"E, 170 m, dry stream valley with various trees and fern, soil washing, 24.XII.2019; **17**: SE Vrises, E Askifou, 35°18'32"N, 24°13'18"E, 880 m, scree slope with *Quercus ilex* and *Arum* undergrowth, soil washing, 25.XII.2019; **18**: SE Vrises, E Askifou, 35°18'22"N, 24°14'06"E, 990 m, scree slope with *Quercus ilex* and *Acer* sp., soil washing, 25.XII.2019; **19**: Psiloritis, NE Livadia, 35°18'56"N, 24°49'07"E, 440 m, stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing near large rocks, 26.XII.2019; **19a**: same data, but litter sifted; **20**: E Malia, N Latsida, 35°16'08"N, 25°34'38"E, 260 m, dry stream valley between olive groves with oak and other trees, soil washing, 27.XII.2019; **21**: SE Malia, Selena Oros, 35°14'50"N, 25°30'56"E, 840 m, rocky calcareous slope with *Quercus ilex* and phrygana, soil washing, 27.XII.2019; **21a**: same data, but litter and soil sifted; **22**: SE Malia, Selena Oros, 35°14'41"N, 25°31'03"E, 860 m, rocky calcareous slope with *Quercus ilex* and phrygana, litter and soil sifted, 27.XII.2019; **23**: NW Ierapetra, NW Males, 35°05'03"N, 25°34'36"E, 510 m, steep stream valley, soil and gravel washing beneath old *Platanus orientalis*, 28.XII.2019; **24**: NW Ierapetra, Selakano, 35°05'14"N, 25°32'48"E, 840 m, rocky stream valley with *Quercus ilex*, soil washing, 28.XII.2019; **25**: NW Ierapetra, Selakano, 35°05'20"N, 25°32'51"E, 840 m, rocky slope near stream with *Quercus ilex*, soil washing, 28.XII.2019; **26**: NW Ierapetra, NE Anatoli, 35°03'02"N, 25°38'59"E, 590 m, steep rocky slope with *Quercus* sp., *Quercus ilex*, and other bushes, stony soil

washing near road margin, 28.XII.2019; **27**: E Agios Nikolaos, S Sfaka, 35°09'00"N, 25°55'26"E, 320 m, narrow dry stream valley with *Quercus ilex*, soil washing, 29.XII.2019; **28**: E Agios Nikolaos, E Mirsini, 35°10'06"N, 25°56'59"E, 320 m, narrow dry stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, *Quercus ilex*, and bushes, soil and gravel washing, 29.XII.2019; **29**: SW Agios Nikolaos, SW Kroustas, 35°07'02"N, 25°37'56"E, 810 m, rocky slope with *Quercus ilex*, soil washing, 30.XII.2019; **30**: SW Agios Nikolaos, SW Kroustas, 35°06'42"N, 25°37'34"E, 930 m, rocky slope with *Quercus ilex* and *Pinus* sp., soil washing, 30.XII.2019.

Descriptions of new species

Paramaurops creticus BRACHAT spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:0ADD6720-1EEC-4E67-90EE-F1DC5B1C9ACE
(Figs 1, 21)

Type material: Holotype ♂: "GR – Crete [19a], Psiloritis, NE Livadia, 35°18'56"N, 24°49'07"E, 440 m, litter sifted, 26.XII.2019, V. Assing / *Paramaurops creticus* spec. nov. ♂, det. Brachat 2.2020 / Holotypus" (cBra).

Etymology: The specific epithet (Latin, adjective) alludes to the restricted distribution of this species.

Description: Body 2.40 mm long, pale reddish-brown, smooth, and with scattered yellowish pubescence. Habitus as in Fig. 1.

Head 0.52 mm long and 0.48 mm broad, postero-laterally with long erect pubescence. Eyes absent, replaced with a stout lateral spine-shaped extension; carinae extending from antennal protuberances very short; vertex posteriorly with a short median carina. Antennae slender, 1.27 mm long; all antennomeres distinctly oblong; antennomeres III–VII twice as long as broad. Maxillary palpomere IV elongate, 0.24 mm long.

Pronotum 0.48 mm long and 0.42 mm broad, without lateral carinae and without protuberances on disc; disc anteriorly with weakly pronounced median carina, basally with a small lateral fovea on either side and with a short median carina, ante-basally with a small median and two small lateral foveae.

Elytra 0.60 mm long and 0.72 mm broad, with three indistinct basal foveae, without impression on disc. Hind wings completely reduced. Metaventricle with a median fovea near posterior margin. Legs long and slender.

Abdomen: tergite IV 0.54 mm long and 0.78 mm broad, basally with a large median and two small and shallow lateral foveae, median fovea densely pubescent, sublateral carinae situated at some distance from lateral margins, oblique, and approximately half as long as tergite.

♂: trochanters and femora unmodified; metatibia with short apical spine; aedeagus 0.30 mm long and shaped as in Fig. 21.

Comparative notes: The new species is distinguished from the similar *Paramaurops kaufmanni* (GANGLBAUER, 1895) and *P. commixtus* (J. MÜLLER, 1928) from the Balkans by distinctly larger body size (*P. kaufmanni* and *P. commixtus*: body length approximately 2.0 mm) and by the shape of the aedeagus.

Distribution: The type locality is situated near Livadia in the north slope of the Psiloritis range. The holotype was sifted from deep litter of *Platanus orientalis* in a stream valley with large rocks at an altitude of 440 m. For a photograph of this locality, which is also the type locality of *Cretotyphlus idanus* ASSING, 2019, *Cephenium idanum* ASSING, 2019, and *C. latius* ASSING, 2019 see figure 175 in ASSING et al. (2019).

Afropselaphus chanianus BRACHAT spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7648FB38-4026-414C-8609-32447D514299
(Figs 2, 22)

Type material: Holotypus ♂: "GR – Crete [1], SW Chania, WSW Lakki, 35°23'53"N, 23°54'38"E, 390 m, stream valley, 21.XII.2019, V. Assing / *Afropselaphus chanianus* spec. nov. ♂ det. Brachat 2.2020 / Holotypus" (cBra).

Etymology: The specific epithet is an adjective derived from Chania, the district where the type locality is situated.

Description: Body 1.60 mm long, reddish-brown, smooth, with scattered long yellowish setae. Habitus as in Fig. 2.

Head 0.37 mm long and 0.26 mm broad; frons with two carinae extending from antennal insertions to frontal foveae; posterior portion between frontal foveae and posterior margin of head shallowly impressed. Eyes small, composed of 7–8 ommatidia, less than half as long as postocular portion. Antenna 0.9 mm long; all antennomeres oblong, antennomeres IX–XI forming a club; antennomere XI as long as the combined length of antennomeres VIII–X. Maxillary palpomere IV club-shaped in apical half.

Pronotum 0.29 mm long and 0.25 mm broad, with three distinct ante-basal foveae. Elytra short, 0.34 mm long and 0.56 mm broad; posterior margin with dense sub-erect pubescence. Metaventricle distinctly domed.

Abdomen: tergite IV 0.34 mm long and 0.56 mm broad, anteriorly with dense scaly pubescence and a deep impression; sternite IV anteriorly without depression.

♂: aedeagus 0.29 mm long and shaped as in Fig. 2; parameres each with three apical setae.

Comparative notes: The new species is highly similar to the geographically close *A. doernfeldi* BRACHAT, 2019 and *A. assingi* BRACHAT, 2019. It is reliably distinguished from them only based on the shape of the aedeagus. For illus-

trations of the aedeagi of *A. doernfeldi* and *A. assingi* see ASSING et al. (2019).

In December 2018, an *Afropselaphus* male was collected practically in the same locality (see ASSING 2019c). This male most likely represents an undescribed species distinguished from *A. chaniamus* by a larger (0.33 mm), apically tapering aedeagus with a long internal structure. Since this structure is extruded in the only specimen available, a formal description is refrained from.

Distribution and natural history: The type locality is situated to the southwest of Chania, West Crete, at an altitude of 390 m. The holotype was collected by washing stony soil with little humus from a stream valley with a very old chestnut tree.

Notes on some species

Lordithon trinotatus (ERICHSON, 1839)

The specimens listed in Tab. 1 represent the first record from Crete.

Cephennium idanum ASSING, 2019

(Fig. 23)

The previously known distribution was confined to the type locality near Livadia in the north slope of the Psiloritis range, Central Crete. In December 2019, the species was recorded also from Selena Oros to the southeast of Malia and another locality to the Northwest of Ierapetra, records that significantly expand the known range towards the east of Crete. The aedeagus of a male from Selena Oros is illustrated in Fig. 23.

Allotyphlus foedatus ASSING, 2019

This species was previously known only from West Crete eastwards to the Askifou plateau. The male from the environs of Livadia in the Psiloritis range considerably expands the known distribution eastwards to Central Crete.

Throbalium creticum COIFFAIT, 1980 and *T. dividuum dividuum* (ERICHSON, 1840)

The original description of *T. creticum* is based on a male holotype and four female paratypes from “Baie de Colpos-Soudas, Chypre” deposited in the Coiffait collection (COIFFAIT 1980). The type locality (“Chypre”) is evidently a lapsus and was rectified by COIFFAIT (1982), who stated that the species was in fact distributed in “Crète”. Nevertheless, it is still indicated for Cyprus in the Palaearctic Catalogue (SCHÜLKE & SMETANA 2015),

which partly explains why *T. creticum* was omitted from the checklist of the Staphylinidae of Crete in ASSING (2019c). Owing to the currently restricted loan policy of the Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris, it was not possible to study the type material in order to clarify the status of the species and the question whether or not it is endemic to the island.

Based on old literature records by KRAATZ (1858) and OERTZEN (1887), *Throbalium dividuum dividuum* is the only *Throbalium* species listed for Crete in ASSING (2019c). In view of the otherwise West Mediterranean distribution of *T. dividuum* there is little doubt that these records in fact refer to *T. creticum*.

Additional records

Andreas Kleeberg (Berlin) communicated additional records from the following localities:

1. S-Crete, Agios Galini, 3.IV.2002, leg. Kleeberg: *Ochtheophilus andalusiacus* (FAGEL, 1957): 8 exs. [det. Makranczy] (cKle); *Ochtheophilus venustus* ROSENHAUER, 1856: 4 exs. [det. Makranczy] (cKle); *Gnypeta rubrior* TOTTENHAM, 1939: 1 ex. (cKle).

2. Central Crete, S Kaneros, Kotsifos Gorge, 5.IV.2002, leg. Kleeberg: *Lesteva nitidicollis* LOHSE & STEEL, 1961: 6 exs. [det. Schülke] (cKle); *Platystethus spinosus* ERICHSON, 1840: 2 exs. [det. Schülke] (cKle); *Aloconota subgrandis* (BRUNDIN, 1954): 1 ex. [det. Assing] (cKle).

3. West Crete, Lake Kournas, 4.IV.2002, leg. Kleeberg: *Carpelimus obesus* (KIESENWETTER, 1844): 3 exs. [det. Kleeberg] (cKle).

4. West Crete, Georgiopolis env., Aspropoliani, 30.IX.–6.X.2002, leg. Kleeberg: *Carpelimus bilineatus* STEPHENS, 1834: 2 exs. [det. Kleeberg] (cKle); *Stenus hospes* ERICHSON, 1840: 18 exs. [det. Puthz] (cKle, cPut); *Stenus brunnipes lepidus* WEISE, 1875: 1 ex. [det. Puthz] (cKle); *Stenus picipes* STEPHENS, 1833: 12 exs. [det. Puthz] (cKle, cPut); *Rugilus orbiculatus* (PAYKULL, 1789): 8 exs. [det. Kleeberg] (cKle); *Aloconota subgrandis* (BRUNDIN, 1954): 1 ex. [det. Assing] (cKle); *Gabrius nigrifulus* (GRAVENHORST, 1802): 8 exs. [det. Schülke] (cKle); *Gabronthus maritimus* (MOTSCHULSKY, 1858): 5 exs. [det. Schülke] (cKle).

5. West Crete, Georgiopolis, beach, 25.IV.1992, leg. Rößner: *Stenistoderus cephalotes* (KRAATZ, 1858): 1 ex. [det. Janák] (cKle).

Ochtheophilus andalusiacus is reported from Crete for the first time.

Tab. 2: Updated checklist of the Staphylinidae recorded from Samos and results of the field trip to Samos conducted by Volker Brachat, Thomas Forcke, and the author in April 2022. Details on the localities/samples are provided at the end of the list. Specimen numbers are given in parentheses behind the sample number. First records of non-endemic species from Samos are marked with an asterisk (*), first records from Greece with two, and first records from Europe with three asterisks. Endemic species are preceded by a "+". For additional footnotes and references for species recorded from Samos before 2017 see the footnotes and references in ASSING (2017b).

The references are abbreviated as follows: A17b = ASSING (2017b); A18c = ASSING (2018c); A19a = ASSING (2019a); Aip = ASSING (in press); App = ASSING (present paper); G19 = GILDENKOV (2019), M14 = MAKRANCZY (2014).

Species	Localities/samples	References
O m a l i i n a e		
<i>Boreaphilus velox</i> (HEER, 1839)		A17b
* <i>Dropephylla perforata</i> (ZANETTI, 1987)	4(1)	App
<i>Omalium cinnamomeum</i> KRAATZ, 1857	10(1), 10a(2), 11(1), 11a(17), 12a(1), 24(1), 29(3), 29a(1), 30(3), 37(1), 47a(3)	A17b, App
<i>Omalium rhodicum</i> ZANETTI & ASSING, 2013		A17b
<i>Omalium rugatum</i> MULSANT & REY, 1880	9a(1), 31(1), 60(17)	A17b, App
<i>Philorinum hopffgarteni</i> EPPELSHEIM, 1892		A17b
P r o t e i n i n a e		
<i>Metopsia assingi</i> ZERCHE, 1998		A17b
<i>Proteinus utrarius</i> ASSING, 2004	3(1), 4(1), 5(75), 6(2), 9(1), 11a(1), 32a(1)	A17b, App
M i c r o p e p l i n a e		
<i>Micropeplus fulvus</i> ERICHSON, 1840	3a(1), 4(3), 5(1), 8(2), 16a(3), 36(1)	A17b, App
<i>Micropeplus staphylinoides</i> (MARSHAM, 1802)	27(2)	A17b, App
P s e l a p h i n a e		
* <i>Batrisodes buqueti</i> (AUBÉ, 1833)	36b(2)	App
* <i>Batrisodes delaporti</i> (AUBÉ, 1833)	1d(1)	App
<i>Biblopectus parvulus</i> BESUCHET, 1975		A17b
* <i>Brachygluta foveola foveola</i> (MOTSCHULSKY, 1840)	41(1)	App
* <i>Brachygluta helferi longispina</i> (REITTER, 1884)	50a(5)	App
<i>Brachygluta spinicoxis fuchsii</i> (PAGANETTI-HUMMLER, 1899)	49(1)	A17b, App
* <i>Brachygluta xanthoptera</i> (REICHENBACH, 1816)	23b(1)	App
<i>Bryaxis anatolicus</i> (SAULCY, 1878)	3(1), 3a(4), 5(1), 8(2), 9a(3), 10a(6), 13a(4), 16a(7), 18a(2), 19(1), 21(1), 24a(4), 29a(2), 30a(1), 34(3), 34a(2), 37(5), 37b(3), 39(1), 40(3), 40a(5), 43(1), 51(2)	A17b, App
<i>Bryaxis pumilus</i> BEKCHIEV & BRACHAT, 2015	8(7), 10(2), 10a(4), 11(2), 11a(32), 12(2), 12a(11), 14a(5), 16a(2), 24a(8), 29a(2), 30(6), 30a(2), 34(1), 36(3), 47(4), 47a(13), 48(9), 51a(1), 54(2)	A17b, App
<i>Bythinus simplicipalpis</i> BRACHAT, 2016		A17b
<i>Claviger</i> spp.	36a(3), 36b(1), 40b(2)	A17b, App
* <i>Euplectus kirbii kirbii</i> DENNY, 1825	36a(3), 36b(2)	App
+ <i>Euplectus meyhohmi</i> BRACHAT, 2017	3(1)	A17b, App
<i>Faronus distinctus</i> BESUCHET, 1999		A17b
+ <i>Namunia cavernicola</i> BESUCHET, 1978		A17b
+ <i>Paramaurops</i> spp. (undescribed) (♀)	10(1), 13(1)	A17b, App
<i>Paratychnus mendax</i> (KIESENWETTER, 1858)		A17b

Species	Localities/samples	References
<i>Tribatus creticus</i> REITTER, 1884		A17b
<i>Trimium caucasicum</i> KOLENATI, 1846	2(1), 3(3), 3a(1), 4(2), 7(1), 8(1), 11a(9), 12(4), 12a(10), 13a(2), 21a(1), 24a(9), 29a(4), 30(2), 30a(3), 33(1), 34(1), 36a(2), 51a(3), 52b(1), 53a(1), 54(1)	A17b, App
+ <i>Trimium</i> sp. (undescribed) (♀)		A17b
+ <i>Tychobythinus brachati</i> BESUCHET, 2008		A17b
<i>Tychus anatolicus</i> BESUCHET, 1964		A17b
+ <i>Tychus kerkisicus</i> (BRACHAT, 2017), comb. nov.	37(1)	A17b, App
<i>Tychus</i> sp. (♀)	12a(1), 37(1)	App
Phloeocharinae		
<i>Phloeocharis longipennis</i> FAUVEL, 1875		A17b
T a c h y p o r i n a e		
<i>Bryoporus multipunctus</i> HAMPE, 1867		A17b
<i>Lordithon bimaculatus</i> (SCHRANK, 1798)		A17b
* <i>Lordithon trinotatus</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)	1d(1)	App
<i>Mycetoporus confinis</i> REY, 1883		A17b
<i>Mycetoporus ignidorsum</i> EPPELSHEIM, 1880	12a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Mycetoporus imperialis</i> BERNHAUER, 1902	11a(1), 12a(2), 31(1), 38(1), 46a(2), 47a(3), 51(1)	A17b, App
<i>Mycetoporus macrocephalus</i> BERNHAUER, 1917		A17b
<i>Mycetoporus monticola</i> FOWLER, 1888		A17b
<i>Mycetoporus reichei</i> (PANDELLÉ, 1869)	3a(1), 8(3), 12a(2), 53(1)	A17b, App
<i>Mycetoporus simillimus</i> FAGEL, 1965	1b(12), 19(1), 33(1), 40(1), 46(1), 46a(11), 47a(19), 48(1), 55(1), 57(7)	A17b, App
<i>Mycetoporus (nigricollis group)</i> sp. (♀)	30(1)	App
<i>Sepedophilus immaculatus</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)		A17b
<i>Sepedophilus obtusus</i> (LUZE, 1902)		A17b
<i>Sepedophilus testaceus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1792)	1a(1), 1d(2), 52a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Tachyporus abner</i> SAULCY, 1865		A17b
<i>Tachyporus caucasicus</i> KOLENATI, 1846		A17b
* <i>Tachyporus hypnorum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)	1c(1)	App
<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)		A17b
H a b r o c e r i n a e		
<i>Habrocerus pisidicus</i> KORGE, 1971	9a(1), 12a(1), 52a(1)	A17b, App
A l e o c h a r i n a e		
<i>Acrotona muscorum</i> (BRISOUT, 1860)		A17b
<i>Aleochara</i> cf. <i>conviva</i> EPPELSHEIM, 1890		A17b
* <i>Aleochara bipustulata</i> (LINNAEUS, 1760)	22(1)	App
<i>Aleochara haematoptera</i> KRAATZ, 1858	23a(3), 49(1)	A17b, App
<i>Aleochara rambouseki</i> LIKOVSKÝ, 1981	1b(1), 13a(1), 14a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Alevonota rufotestacea</i> (KRAATZ, 1856)		A17b
<i>Aloconota aegea</i> ASSING, 2016	23a(1), 23b(3)	A17b, App
* <i>Aloconota cambrica</i> (WOLLASTON, 1855)	23b(3)	App
<i>Aloconota samia</i> ASSING, 2016	60(2)	A17b, App

Species	Localities/samples	References
<i>Atheta aeneicollis</i> (SHARP, 1869)	3(1), 8(1), 9(6), 10(3), 10a(2), 11(1), 12(1), 12a(7), 13(4), 13a(1), 14a(3), 23a(1), 24a(3), 27(1), 28(2), 29(17), 30(3), 31(2), 32a(3), 33(2), 36(1), 36b(1), 37(1), 40a(1), 43(4), 44(1), 46a(2), 47(4), 47a(2), 48(4), 51(1), 55(1), 60(2)	A17b, App
* <i>Atheta amicula</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)	47(1)	App
<i>Atheta speculum</i> (KRAATZ, 1856)		A17b
* <i>Atheta tecta</i> ASSING, spec. nov.	41(2), 41a(3), 50a(1), 56(1)	App
<i>Atheta trinotata</i> (KRAATZ, 1856)		A17b
<i>Atheta pulchra</i> (KRAATZ, 1856)		A17b
<i>Atheta (Microdota) sp.</i> (♀)		A17b
<i>Atheta (Mocyta) spp.</i>	8(1), 11a(2), 12a(1), 24a(2), 36a(1), 47a(29), 50a(1), 56(11), 60(5)	A17b, App
<i>Brundinia meridionalis</i> (MULSANT & REY, 1853)	35(1), 35a(2), 45(3), 50(2), 50a(4)	A17b, App
<i>Cousya defecta</i> (MULSANT & REY, 1875)	1c(1)	A17b, App
<i>Cypha spathulata</i> ASSING, 2007		A17b
<i>Cypha cf. tarsalis</i> (LUZE, 1902) (♀)		A17b
<i>Dinusa cretica</i> ASSING, 2013		A17b
<i>Geostiba maxiana</i> (TIKHOMIROVA, 1973)	1b(4), 42(1), 46(2), 46a(12)	A17b, App
<i>Geostiba oertzeni</i> (EPPELSHEIM, 1888)	(4), 9(1), 9a(1), 10(1), 10a(5), 11(1), 24a(1), 28(3), 29(2), 30(3), 30a(1), 33(1), 34(7), 36(1), 37(7), 37a(1), 37b(4), 39(1), 40a(5), 51(9), 51a(1), 52a(1), 52b(1)	A17b, App
+ <i>Geostiba plicipennis</i> ASSING, 2015	1a(1), 3(1)	A17b, App
* <i>Hydrosmecta cultellata</i> ASSING, spec. nov.	60(4)	App
* <i>Hydrosmecta insularum</i> ASSING, 2019	23b(4)	App
* <i>Hydrosmecta sp.</i> [♀]	23b(6)	App
* <i>Ischnoglossa minor</i> (AUBÉ, 1863)		Aip, App
<i>Ischnoglossa turcica</i> WUNDERLE, 1992		A17b
<i>Leptusa samia</i> ASSING, 2004	1d(1), 11a(1), 36(1)	A17b, App
<i>Liogluta longiuscula</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	12a(3), 47a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Liogluta sp.</i>	60(1)	App
<i>Maurachelia roubali</i> (LOHSE, 1970)		A17b
*** <i>Meotica truncata</i> ASSING, 2004	26(2)	App
* <i>Myllaena graeca</i> KRAATZ, 1858	31(2), 31a(3)	App
* <i>Myllaena infuscata</i> KRAATZ, 1858	50(1)	App
<i>Myllaena intermedia</i> ERICHSON, 1837	41a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Myrmecopora convexula</i> ASSING, 1997	17(1)	A17b, App
<i>Ocalea brachyptera</i> FAGEL, 1971		A17b
<i>Oligota pumilio</i> KIESENWETTER, 1858	24a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Oxypoda acutissima</i> ASSING, 2006		A17b
<i>Oxypoda flavicornis</i> KRAATZ, 1856		A17b
*** <i>Oxypoda flavicaudata</i> ASSING, 2006	24a(1), 47a(1), 48(1)	App
*** <i>Oxypoda gladiatoria</i> ASSING, 2006	12a(1), 46a(1), 57(1)	App
* <i>Oxypoda cf. haemorrhoea</i> (MANNERHEIM, 1830)	47(1)	App

Species	Localities/samples	References
+ <i>Oxypoda kerkisica</i> ASSING, 2015	57(3)	A17b, App
<i>Oxypoda libanotica</i> FAGEL, 1965		A17b
<i>Oxypoda lurida</i> WOLLASTON, 1857	47(2), 53a(1), 57(1), 60(2)	A17b, App
<i>Oxypoda rectacia</i> ASSING, 2019	1a(1), 1b(12), 3a(1), 12a(1), 14a(1), 32a(1), 40a(2), 42(1), 46a(7), 47a(1), 47a(1), 60(1)	A17b, A19a, App
<i>Oxypoda scheerpeltziana</i> (FAGEL, 1968)		A17b
<i>Oxypoda turcica</i> ZERCHE, 1999		A17b
<i>Oxypoda vicina</i> KRAATZ, 1858		A17b
<i>Parocysa longitarsis</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)	23(1), 23a(2), 23b(1), 49(3), 60(4)	A17b, App
<i>Piochardia reitteri</i> (WASMANN, 1894)	58(1)	A17b, App
<i>Pseudosemiris kaufmanni</i> (EPPELSHEIM, 1887)		A17b
<i>Taxicera moczarskii</i> (BERNHAEUER, 1914)		A17b
O x y t e l i n a e		
* <i>Anotylus clypeonitens</i> (PANDELLÉ, 1867)	23b(1), 49(1)	App
* <i>Anotylus complanatus</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)	8(1)	App
<i>Anotylus inustus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)	1b(1), 8(5), 10a(3), 11a(1), 11b(1), 12as(4), 13(1), 14a(1), 22(6), 23(2), 23a(11), 23b(3), 24a(2), 29(1), 33(1), 34(1), 36(1), 45(1), 49(1), 60(12)	A17b, App
* <i>Bledius bedelianus</i> SCHÜLKE, spec. nov.	23a(3), 23b(2), 49(9), 60(1)	App
<i>Bledius frisius</i> LOHSE, 1978	35(14), 35a(2)	A17b, App
<i>Bledius furcatus</i> (OLIVIER, 1811)	35(23), 35a(12)	A17b, App
<i>Bledius unicornis</i> (GERMAR, 1825)	35(27), 35a(12), 50(4), 50a(3)	A17b, App
* <i>Carpelimus bilineatus</i> (STEPHENS, 1834)	60(2)	App
* <i>Carpelimus corticinus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)	41a(1), 60(6)	App
* <i>Carpelimus fuliginosus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	60(1)	App
* <i>Carpelimus gracilis</i> (MANNERHEIM, 1830)	60(1)	App
* <i>Carpelimus similis</i> (SMETANA, 1967)	60(1)	App
* <i>Carpelimus simplicicollis</i> (WOLLASTON, 1857) ¹⁾		A17b, App, G19
* <i>Euphania ambulans</i> ASSING, spec. nov.	35a(2)	App
<i>Ochtheophilus andalusiacus</i> (FAGEL, 1957)	49(1), 60(3)	App, M14
<i>Planeustomus cephalotes</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)		A17b
<i>Platystethus spinosus</i> ERICHSON, 1840		A17b
* <i>Thinodromus bodemeyeri</i> (BERNHAEUER, 1902)	60(1)	App
S t e n i n a e		
<i>Stenus aceris</i> STEPHENS, 1833	8(1), 9a(1), 24a(1), 30(1), 31(8), 31a(7), 37a(1), 41(1), 41a(1), 50a(1), 56(2)	A17b, App
<i>Stenus brunnipes lepidus</i> WEISE, 1875		A17b
* <i>Stenus callidus</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1848	41(1), 41a(2)	App
<i>Stenus glacialis</i> HEER, 1839	1c(1)	A17b, App
<i>Stenus hospes</i> ERICHSON, 1840		A17b
<i>Stenus maculiger</i> WEISE, 1875	9a(1), 23a(1), 31(5), 31a(2), 49(2), 59(1), 60(14)	A17b, App
<i>Stenus parciior</i> BERNHAEUER, 1929		A17b

Species	Localities/samples	References
<i>Stenus turbulentus</i> BONDROIT, 1912	8(2), 9a(6), 9b(1), 12a(1), 36b(1), 48(1), 37a(1), 39(1), 41(1), 46a(8), 55(1), 57(1)	A17b, App
<i>Stenus turcicus</i> BERNHAUER, 1912	23(1)	A17b, App
S c y d m a e n i n a e		
+ <i>Cephennium ambulans</i> ASSING, spec. nov. ¹⁾		A17b, App
+ <i>Cephennium monstrans</i> ASSING, spec. nov. ¹⁾		A17b, App
<i>Chevolatia</i> sp. (♀)		A17b
+ <i>Euconnus ambelolicus</i> MEYBOHM, 2017	1(1), 8(9), 10a(13), 11a(4), 30(7), 30a(1), 36(1), 40b(1), 51(1), 52(3)	A17b, App
<i>Euconnus intrusus</i> (SCHAUM, 1844)	50a(1)	A17b, App
+ <i>Euconnus kerkisicus</i> MEYBOHM, 2017	13a(2), 24a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Euconnus samius</i> MEYBOHM, 2017	10a(1), 11(3), 12(2), 14a(1), 16a(1), 24a(1), 34a(1), 54(1)	A17b, App
<i>Euconnus</i> sp. (♀; undescribed)		A17b
<i>Eutheia</i> sp.		A17b
<i>Leptomastax simonis</i> STUSSINER, 1881	12a(1), 13(1), 24(2), 28(1), 37(1), 37a(1), 53(1)	A17b, App
* <i>Scydmaenus cornutus</i> MOTSCHULSKY, 1844	36a(3), 36b(3)	App
<i>Scydmorephes amphimykalicus</i> MEYBOHM, spec. nov.	14a(2)	A17b ¹⁾ , App
<i>Stenichnus amphimykalicus</i> MEYBOHM, spec. nov.		A17b ¹⁾ , App
** <i>Stenichnus cribrum</i> (SAULCY, 1880)	36a(10), 36b(3), 40b(1)	A17b ¹⁾ , App
+ <i>Stenichnus samius</i> MEYBOHM, spec. nov.	13a(1), 24a(1)	A17b ¹⁾ , App
P s e u d o p s i n a e		
<i>Pseudopsis sulcata</i> NEWMAN, 1834		A17b
L e p t o t y p h l i n a e		
+ <i>Cretotyphlus kerkisicus</i> ASSING, spec. nov.	18(1)	App
+ <i>Cretotyphlus</i> sp.	5(1), 12(1), 38(1)	App
P a e d e r i n a e		
<i>Astenus bimaculatus</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)		A17b
<i>Astenus procerus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)		A17b
<i>Astenus thoracicus</i> (BAUDI DI SELVE, 1857)		A17b
<i>Domene stilicina</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)	56(1)	A17b, App
<i>Leptobium gracile</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A17b
+ <i>Leptobium samium</i> ASSING, 2009	1a(3), 1c(1)	A17b, App
<i>Lobrathium rugipenne</i> (HOCHHUTH, 1851)	11b(2), 23(/2), 23a(2), 31a(1), 60(5)	A17b, App
<i>Medon dilutus pythonissa</i> (SAULCY, 1865)	47a(1), 53(2)	A17b, App
<i>Medon fuscus</i> (MANNERHEIM, 1830)		A17b
<i>Medon lydicus</i> BORDONI, 1980	8(4), 10a(2), 11a(9), 12a(9), 14a(3), 29(1), 30(3), 32a(1), 37b(1), 40a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Medon maronitus</i> (SAULCY, 1865)	52a(1)	A17b, App
<i>Medon semiobscurus</i> (FAUVEL, 1875)	4(1), 8(1), 9a(1), 10(3), 10a(6), 12a(1), 20(2), 24a(3), 32a(1), 40a(2), 53(1), 54(1), 55(1)	A17b, App
<i>Medon subfuscus</i> FAGEL, 1969		A17b
<i>Ochthephilum brevipenne</i> (MULSANT & REY, 1861)	35(2), 40a(2), 45(1)	A17b, App

Species	Localities/samples	References
<i>Paederus littoralis</i> GRAVENHORST, 1802	40a(1)	A17b, App
* <i>Pseudomedon obscurellus</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)	60(15)	App
<i>Rugilus lesbius</i> ASSING, 2005	9a(3), 11a(1), 23(1), 31(2), 31a(5)	A17b, App
* <i>Scopaeus cameroni</i> COIFFAIT, 1968	60(1)	App
* <i>Scopaeus gracilis</i> (SPERK, 1835)	23b(2), 60(1)	App
<i>Scopaeus haemusensis</i> FRISCH, 1997		A17b
+ <i>Sunius ambelosicus</i> ASSING, 2015		A17b
+ <i>Sunius geiseri</i> ASSING, 2009		A17b
* <i>Throbalium cycladicum</i> (KOCH, 1937)	35(2)	App
S t a p h y l i n i n a e		
* <i>Acylophorus glaberrimus</i> (HERBST, 1784)	41(1)	App
<i>Astrapaeus ulmi</i> (ROSSI, 1790)		A17b
<i>Erichsonius subopacus</i> (HOCHHUTH, 1851)	31a(1), 60(2)	A17b, App
<i>Gabrius astutoides</i> (STRAND, 1946)		A17b
<i>Gabrius nigritulus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	31(1), 60(1)	A17b, App
* <i>Gauropterus fulgidus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1787)	23(2)	App
* <i>Gyrophypnus fracticornis</i> (MÜLLER, 1776)	11a(1)	App
<i>Heterothops dissimilis</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	13b(1)	A17b ²⁾ , App
<i>Heterothops</i> sp. (♀)	47a(1)	App
<i>Ocypus mus</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	18a(1), 60(1)	A17b, App
<i>Orthidus cribratus cribratus</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)	45(1)	A17b, App
<i>Othius laeviusculus</i> STEPHENS, 1833		A17b
<i>Othius lapidicola</i> MÄRKEL & KIESENWETTER, 1848	1b(1), 4(1), 42(1), 44(2), 46(1), 46a(6), 47a(2), 57(5)	A17b, App
<i>Philonthus concinnus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A17b
<i>Philonthus quisquiliarius</i> (GYLLENHAL, 1810)	22(3), 35a(6), 41(5), 41a(4), 45(6), 49(6), 50a(2)	A17b, App
* <i>Philonthus rufimanus rufimanus</i> ERICHSON, 1840	23(3), 23a(7), 49(4)	App
<i>Quedius cohaesus</i> EPPELSHEIM, 1888	1a(2), 1b(2)	A17b ⁴⁾
<i>Quedius curtidens</i> SMETANA, 1967		A17b
* <i>Quedius fissus</i> GRIDELLI, 1938	60(1)	App
<i>Quedius</i> cf. <i>hellenicus</i> ASSING, 2017 (♀)		A17b
<i>Quedius hermonensis</i> COIFFAIT, 1963		A17b ³⁾ , A18c
* <i>Quedius humeralis</i> STEPHENS, 1832	31(2), 60(4)	App
<i>Quedius job</i> COIFFAIT, 1963		A17b, App
* <i>Quedius levicollis</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	56(4)	App
<i>Quedius nemoralis</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1848	11a(1), 31a(1), 40a(1), 47a(1), 57(1), 60(3)	A17b, App
<i>Quedius ortrudae</i> KORGE, 1971	33(1)	A17b ⁵⁾ , A18c, App
<i>Quedius scintillans</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)	31(2), 31a(1), 45(1), 56(22), 60(5)	A17b, App
<i>Quedius semiaeneus</i> (STEPHENS, 1833)		A17b
<i>Quedius umbrinus</i> ERICHSON, 1839	31(9), 31a(5),	A17b, App
** <i>Quedius vicinus</i> (MÉNÉTRIÉS, 1832)	41a(2)	App
* <i>Stenistoderus cephalotes</i> (KRAATZ, 1858)	35(1), 45(3)	App

Species	Localities/samples	References
<i>Xantholinus chiosicus</i> ASSING, 2015	1a(1), 1b(1), 3a(1), 4(2)	A17b, App
<i>Xantholinus rufipennis</i> ERICHSON, 1839	56(1)	A17b, App
<i>Xantholinus varnensis</i> COIFFAIT, 1972		A17b

Footnotes: ¹⁾ listed as unnamed species in ASSING (2017b); ²⁾ listed as *Heterothops minutus* WOLLASTON, 1860 in ASSING (2017b) (misidentification); ³⁾ listed as *Quedius rugosipennis* FÄGEL, 1969 in ASSING (2017b) (synonym); ⁴⁾ listed as *Quedius pseudonigriceps* REITTER, 1909 in ASSING (2017b) (synonym); ⁵⁾ listed as *Quedius nivicola* KIESENWETTER, 1858 in ASSING (2017b) (misidentification).

The Staphylinidae fauna of Samos

According to the latest contribution to the fauna of Samos (ASSING 2017b), 157 species, 17 of them endemic, were known from the island. Revisions and a faunistic article published in the meantime (ASSING 2018c, 2019a, GILDENKOV 2019) and a previously overlooked revision (MAKRANCZY 2014) resulted in taxonomic changes and records of three additional species.

A field trip conducted to Samos in April 2022 by Volker Brachat (primary focus on Pselaphinae and Scydmaeninae), Thomas Forcke (primary focus on Carabidae), and the author (primary focus on endogean Staphylinidae) yielded more than 1500 specimens belonging to at least 136 species, with nearly 50 species recorded from Samos for the first time, some of them even representing first records from Greece and/or even the whole of Europe (Tab. 2).

Despite exhaustive efforts at taking soil samples (in all more than 50 large samples) and extracting them by soil washing, the results of the 2022 field trip were remarkably poor regarding the endogean fauna, a phenomenon most likely caused by the preceding, exceptionally hot and dry summer of 2021. Only four specimens of Leptotyphlinae, each of them in a different sample, and not a single specimen of *Cephenium* MÜLLER & KUNZE, 1822 or Anillina (Carabidae) were collected, although at least two *Cephenium* and three Anillina species were already known from the island (ASSING 2017b, GIACHINO & VAILATI 2019). Similarly, only few Staphylinidae were found by turning stones, much fewer than during similar field trips in 2015 and 2017.

As many as ten species, two of Aleocharinae, two of Oxytelinae, one of Leptotyphlinae, and five of Scydmaeninae are newly described. Some additional species of Pselaphinae (*Claviger* spp., *Paramaurops* spp., *Trimium* sp., *Tychus* sp.?) and Scydmaeninae (*Euconnus* sp.) are most likely undescribed, but cannot be named for want of males or require a DNA-based approach (*Claviger* spp.).

Currently including a total of 199 named species, 15 of them endemic, plus additional unnamed or unidentified species, the known diversity of the Staphylinidae fauna of Samos is greater than those of all other Aegean islands. For a compilation of the species numbers recorded from other Mediterranean islands see ASSING (2019c).

Localities/samples: April 2022: 1: SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°46'33"N, 26°48'38"E, 940 m, grassy clearing with *Pinus* and *Quercus ilex*, soil washing, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **1a:** same data, but litter and pine bark sifted, and under stones, leg. Brachat & Forcke; **1b:** same data, but litter of *Quercus ilex* sifted, 15.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Forcke; **1c:** same data, but under stones, 15.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Forcke; **1d:** same data, but dead pine sifted, 15.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **2:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°46'41"N, 26°48'30"E, 930 m, N-slope with large rocks, pine and *Quercus ilex*, and fern undergrowth, soil washing, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **3:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°46'56"N, 26°48'11"E, 910 m, N-slope with *Castanea*, soil washing, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **3a:** same data, but litter sifted, leg. Brachat; **4:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°47'00"N, 26°48'05"E, 900 m, N-slope with *Castanea*, soil washing, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **5:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°47'13"N, 26°47'59"E, 870 m, soil washing beneath old *Platanus orientalis*, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **6:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°47'26"N, 26°48'00"E, 770 m, dry stream valley with bushes and small trees, soil washing, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **7:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°47'30"N, 26°47'51"E, 750 m, *Castanea* forest, soil washing near large rock, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **8:** SSW Agios Konstantinos, Oros Ambelos: N-slope, 37°47'48"N, 26°48'23"E, 370 m, *Platanus orientalis* litter near small stream sifted, 2.IV.2022, leg. Assing, Brachat & Forcke; **9:** SE Agios Konstantinos, Nightingale Valley, 37°47'25"N, 26°49'58"E, 110 m, stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing, 3.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **9a:** same data, but litter sifted, leg. Brachat & Forcke; **9b:** same data, but dead *Platanus* trunk sifted, leg. Brachat; **10:** SE Agios Konstantinos, road to Manolates, 37°47'14"N, 26°49'23"E, 230 m, stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing (scree) near large rock, leg. Assing; **10a:** same data, but litter near large rock sifted, leg. Assing, Brachat & Forcke; **11:** SE Agios Konstantinos, road to Manolates, 37°47'33"N, 26°49'30"E, 120 m, stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing near large rocks, 3.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **11a:** same data, but litter near large rocks sifted, leg. Assing, Brachat &

Forcke; **11b**: same data, but stream bank, leg. Assing & Forcke; **12**: W Pirgos, 37°43'21"N, 26°45'46"E, 390 m, stream valley on S-slope, soil washing near stream, 4.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **12a**: same data, but litter near stream sifted, leg. Assing, Brachat & Forcke; **13**: SW Karlovassi, N Kastania, 37°45'36"N, 26°40'55"E, 250 m, stream valley with *Platanus*, *Acer*, and *Populus*, soil washing, 4.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **13a**: same data, but litter sifted, leg. Brachat & Forcke; **13b**: running on stone, leg. Assing; **14**: Oros Kerkis: NW-slope, NE Kalithea, track to Agios Dimitrias, 37°44'35"N, 26°37'02"E, 600 m, stream valley with very old *Platanus* and old *Pinus*, soil washing near *Platanus* trunks, 5.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **14a**: same data, but litter near *Platanus* trunks sifted, leg. Brachat; **15**: Oros Kerkis: NW-slope, NE Kalithea, track to Agios Dimitrias, 37°44'35"N, 26°37'02"E, 620 m, stream valley with very old *Platanus*, soil washing near *Platanus* and near rocks above track, 5.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **16**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°44'25"N, 26°39'24"E, 780 m, dry stream valley with pine and *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing, 6.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **16a**: same data, but litter sifted, leg. Assing & Brachat; **17**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°44'22"N, 26°39'14"E, 740 m, track margin, nest of black *Messor*, 6.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **18**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°44'33"N, 26°39'28"E, 740 m, dry stream valley with *Quercus ilex* and *Pinus*, soil washing, 6.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **18a**: same data, but track margin, under stone, leg. Brachat; **19**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°44'36"N, 26°39'29"E, 750 m, pine forest, dry stream valley with old *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing beneath *Platanus*, 6.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **20**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°44'42"N, 26°39'21"E, 680 m, dry stream valley near road margin, soil washing (fine gravel), 6.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **21**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°45'09"N, 26°39'15"E, 640 m, pine forest, dry stream valley with old *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing, 6.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **21a**: same data, but dry stream valley, litter sifted, 6.IV.2022, leg. Brachat; **22**: Karlovassi, 37°47'54"N, 26°42'03"E, 5 m, river bank, 6.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **23**: E Karlovassi, 37°47'14"N, 26°43'40"E, 30 m, river bank, 6.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **23a**: same data, but 14.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **23b**: same data, but treading, washing, and floating, 16.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Forcke; **24**: W Karlovassi, Potami Waterfalls, 37°47'11"N, 26°40'05"E, 30 m, stream valley with mixed forest, soil washing, 7.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **24a**: same data, but litter sifted, 7.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Brachat; **25**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°45'14"N, 26°39'13"E, 630 m, dry stream valley on slope with old *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing, 7.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **26**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°45'24"N, 26°39'34"E, 610 m, ruderal stream valley, soil washing, 7.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **27**: Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, just above Agios Nikolaos, 37°46'09"N, 26°39'51"E, 390 m, ruderal slope with chestnut and olive trees, soil washing, 7.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **28**: S Agios Konstantinos, 37°48'18"N, 26°48'45"E, 50 m, ruderal trees and bushes, soil washing, 8.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **29**: S Agios Konstantinos, 37°48'09"N, 26°48'46"E, 120 m, stream valley in pine forest with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing near rock, 8.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **29a**: same data, but litter near rock sifted, 8.IV.2022, leg. Brachat; **30**: SE Agios Konstantinos, road to Manolates, 37°47'14"N, 26°49'23"E, 230 m, stream valley with *Platanus orientalis*, soil washing (scree) near large rock, 8.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **30a**: same data, but litter near large rock sifted, 8.IV.2022, leg. Brachat; **31**: SE Karlovassi, 37°47'16"N, 26°43'54"E, 60 m, stream bank, under reed, 8.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **31a**: same data, but 14.IV.2022; **32**: S Vourliotes, 37°46'02"N, 26°51'23"E, 540 m, stream valley, soil washing near stream and near large rocks (coarse sand), 9.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **32a**: same data, but litter near large rocks sifted, leg. Brachat; **33**: S Vourliotes, 37°46'06"N, 26°51'09"E, 600 m, soil washing on slope near large rocks (dark soil with stones), 9.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **34**: S Vourliotes, 37°45'52"N, 26°50'26"E, 670 m, stream valley in shade of large rock wall, soil washing beneath *Quercus ilex* (dark soil with stones), 9.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **34a**: same data, but *Platanus* bark and litter around old *Platanus orientalis* sifted, 9.IV.2022, leg. Brachat; **35**: Psili Ammos, Alyki wetland, salt meadow, 37°42'23"N, 27°00'31"E, 1 m, 9.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **35a**: Psili Ammos, Alyki wetland, 37°42'31"N, 27°00'27"E, 5 m, salt meadow, 10.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **36**: S Agios Konstantinos, Manolates, 37°47'02"N, 26°49'28"E, 330 m, soil washing near old *Platanus orientalis*, 10.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **36a**: same data, but dead wood with *Lasius brunneus* sifted, leg. Assing & Brachat; **36b**: same data, but dead wood with *Lasius brunneus* sifted, 13.IV.2022, leg. Brachat; **37**: S Agios Konstantinos, SW Manolates, 37°46'50"N, 26°49'20"E, 430 m, dry stream valley, soil washing under deciduous trees with rocks (scree), 10.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **37a**: same data, but soil washing near large rocks in ivy (dark soft soil with few stones); **37b**: same data, but litter on slope with deciduous trees sifted, leg. Brachat; **38**: S Agios Konstantinos, SW Manolates, 37°46'50"N, 26°48'53"E, 640 m, dry stream valley, soil washing (stony soil on slope with small trees), 10.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **39**: S Agios Konstantinos, SW Manolates, 37°46'47"N, 26°48'56"E, 660 m, soil washing in dry stream valley beneath old *Platanus orientalis* (stony soil), 10.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **40**: S Agios Konstantinos, SW Manolates, 37°46'38"N, 26°48'58"E, 710 m, soil washing beneath old oak near rocks (stony dark soil), 10.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **40a**: same data, but oak litter sifted, leg. Brachat; **40b**: track margin, under stone with *Lasius* sp., leg. Brachat; **41**: W Psili Ammos, 37°42'43"N, 26°59'06"E, 3 m, wetland, 10.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **41a**: same data, but 11.IV.2022; **42**: SE Paleokastro, 37°43'26"N, 27°02'40"E, 110 m, grassy slope with old oak tree, soil washing, 11.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **43**: SE Paleokastro, 37°43'24"N, 27°02'34"E, 80 m, dry stream valley, soil washing on slope beneath *Quercus ilex*, 11.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **44**: SE Paleokastro, 37°43'25"N, 27°02'29"E, 80 m, grassy slope with young *Quercus ilex*, soil washing (small sample), 11.IV.2022,

leg. Assing; **45**: W Pythagorio, 37°41'29"N, 26°55'44"E, 5 m, swamp, 11.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **46**: SE Paleokastro, 37°43'31"N, 27°03'22"E, 200 m, calcareous grassy slope with abandoned olive and other trees, soil washing near dead tree (shallow reddish soil with small stones), 12.IV.2022, leg. Assing, **46a**: same data, but litter near rocks and old olive tree sifted, leg. Assing & Brachat; **47**: W Vathi, Kamara, 37°44'55"N, 27°00'30"E, 150 m, between large vertical rock and road margin, soil washing below *Quercus ilex* (deep soft black soil with large stones), 12.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **47a**: same data, but litter of *Quercus ilex* sifted, 12.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Brachat; **48**: N Vathi, coast road, 37°47'12"N, 26°57'29"E, 10 m, slope with various deciduous trees, bushes, and *Rubus*, soil washing (deep soft black soil with large stones), 12.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **49**: E Myli, 37°40'39"N, 26°52'19"E, 15 m, river bank, 12.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **50**: W Psili Ammos, 37°42'32"N, 26°59'20"E, 3 m, reed and salt meadow 12.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **50a**: same data, but 13.IV.2022; **51**: S Agios Konstantinos, E Manolates, 37°46'57"N, 26°49'51"E, 370 m, dark stream valley, soil washing (deep stony soil), 13.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **51a**: same data, but litter sifted, leg. Brachat; **52**: S Agios Konstantinos, E Manolates, 37°46'51"N, 26°49'55"E, 380 m, dark dry stream valley, soil washing (stony soil), 13.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **52a**: same data, but soil washing under dead trunk (dark stony soil); **52b**: same data, but litter under dead trunk sifted, leg. Brachat; **53**: S Agios Konstantinos, E Manolates, 37°46'47"N, 26°50'02"E, 380 m, soil washing beneath oak tree, 13.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **53a**: same data, but under stone, leg. Brachat; **54**: S Agios Konstantinos, E Manolates, 37°46'35"N, 26°49'55"E, 420 m, stream valley, soil washing, 13.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **55**: S Agios Konstantinos, 37°47'13"N, 26°49'46"E, 280 m, grassy slope with trees and bushes, soil washing beneath tree (deep dark stony soil), 13.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **56**: W Psili Ammos, 37°42'43"N, 26°59'18"E, 10 m, arable land, 13.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **57**: Oros Kerkis, 37°43'26"N, 26°38'10"E, 1210 m, litter, grass, and moss beneath *Juniperus* and cushion plants sifted, 14.IV.2022, leg. Assing; **58**: Oros Kerkis, 37°45'N, 26°40'E, 820 m, under stone, *Cataglyphis nodus* nest, 14.IV.2022, leg. Brachat; **59**: Agios Konstantinos, 37°48'13"N, 26°49'37"E, 20 m, stream bank, 15.IV.2022, leg. Forcke; **60**: W Karlovassi, Potami, 37°47'11"N, 26°40'05"E, 30 m, stream bank, treading, washing, and floating, 16.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Forcke.

Notes on some species and additional records

Euplectus meyhohmi BRACHAT, 2017

According to Volker Brachat (e-mail 22 July, 2022), the elytra have four basal foveae, not three as indicated in the original description.

Tychus kerkisicus (BRACHAT, 2017), comb. nov.

Paratyclus kerkisicus BRACHAT, 2017: 107.

This species was originally attributed to *Paratyclus* BESUCHET, 1960 primarily because of the elongated maxillary palpomeres IV. Based on a reassessment of other external and sexual characters, however, it belongs to the genus *Tychus* LEACH, 1817 (Volker Brachat, e-mail 22 July, 2022).

Liogluta aloconotoides (BENICK, 1940), comb. nov.

(Figs 4, 24)

Atheta (*Glossola*) *aloconotoides* BENICK, 1940: 180 f.

Aloconota (*Aloconota*) *aloconotoides*: SCHÜLKE & SMETANA (2015)

Type material examined: Holotype ♀: “♀ / Trento, Pechlaner / Ci. Tombea, 13.6.35 / *Atheta grandicornis* Fauv. / *Atheta aloconotoides* ♀, Typus, G. Bck / wohl zu *Liogluta* J. V. / *aloconotoides*, det. Zanetti '96 / MHNG ENTO 00096512 / *Liogluta aloconotoides* (Benick), det. V. Assing 2022” (MHNG).

Comment: The original description is based on a female holotype and an unspecified number of paratypes (“in mehreren Exemplaren”) from “Ci. Tombea” (BENICK 1940). In order to clarify if the female of *Liogluta* sp. (see Tab. 2) is conspecific with this species, the holotype was examined. It undoubtedly belongs to *Liogluta* THOMSON, 1858. The habitus and the shape of the spermatheca of the holotype are illustrated in Figs 4, 24.

Ischnoglossa (*Xenodota*) *minor* (AUBÉ, 1863)

When preparing a taxonomic note on the genus *Ischnoglossa* KRAATZ, 1856, a female of *I. minor* from Samos, the first record of this species from Greece, was examined (ASSING in press). The data are as follows: 1 ♀, Samos, N Psili Ammos, 37°43'N, 26°59'E, 90 m, under bark near stream, 19.IV.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm (cAss).

Meotica truncata ASSING, 2004

Meotica truncata was originally described based on material from Antalya (ASSING 2004b) and subsequently reported also from other localities in various South Turkish provinces (Izmir, Aydın, Isparta, Niğde, Mersin, Kahramanmaraş, Kayseri) (ASSING & VOGEL 2019). The specimens from Samos represent the first records from Samos, Greece, and Europe.

Oxypoda flavocaudata ASSING, 2006

This species was previously known only from South Turkey, from Muğla in the west to Mersin in the east (ASSING 2006, 2007). The specimens from Samos represent the first records from Samos, Greece, and Europe.

Oxypoda gladiatoria ASSING, 2006

The previously known distribution was confined to South Turkey (Muğla, Antalya) and Cyprus (ASSING 2006). The specimens from Samos represent the first records from Samos, Greece, and Europe.

Oxypoda rectacia ASSING, 2019

According to a recent revision (ASSING 2019a), the material listed in ASSING (2017b) as *Oxypoda* cf. *nova* BERNHAUER, 1902 belongs to *O. rectacia*.

Carpelimus simplicicollis (WOLLASTON, 1857)

The female listed in ASSING (2017b) as *Carpelimus* sp. was identified by GILDENKOV (2019) as *C. simplicicollis*.

Ochtheophilus andalusiacus (FAGEL, 1957)

This species was not listed in ASSING (2017b), but had been recorded from Samos by MAKRANCZY (2014).

Stenichnus cribrum (SAULCY, 1880)

According to SCHÜLKE & SMETANA (2015), this species had been reported only from the Caucasus region (Georgia; Russian South European territory). The specimens from Samos represent the first records from Greece.

Throbalium cycladicum (KOCH, 1937)

(Figs 40–57)

Lathrobium (*Throbalium*) *cycladicum* KOCH, 1937: 260 ff.

Lathrobium (*Throbalium*) *biblicum* KOCH, 1937: 262 f.; **syn. nov.**

Throbalium adanense KOCH, 1939: 436 f.; **syn. nov.**

Throbalium kosianum BORDONI, 2020: 223 f.; **syn. nov.**

Type material examined: *Lathrobium cycladicum*: Holotype ♂ [abdomen (except segment VIII) and aedeagus missing]: “Naxos, Graecia / Prep. microscop. No. 1429 / Cotype” (NHMB).

Lathrobium biblicum: Holotype ♂ [aedeagus missing]: “96 / Atlith, Palestine, 22–27.8.1935, A. Rabinovitch cep.

/ *Lathrobium* (*Throbalium*) *biblicum* Koch, det. C. Koch / Type / Holotype 1956 det. Kamp / Coll. G. Frey NMB / *Throbalium cycladicum* (Koch), det. V. Assing 2022” (NHMB).

Throbalium adanense: Holotype ♂: “Adana, Asm., 4.VI.1934, Neubert / Museum Frey Tutzing / *Th. adanense* Koch, det. C. Koch / Type / Coll. G. Frey NMB / *Throbalium cycladicum* (Koch), det. V. Assing 2022” (NHMB).

Additional material examined: GREECE: main-

land: 1 ♂, Pieria, E Korinos, 40°19'N, 22°38'E, 0 m, salt meadow, 20.X.2021, leg. Forcke (cAss); 3 ♀ ♀, Chalkidiki, Kassandra, 15.VIII.1994, leg. Eifler (cAss); 6 ♂ ♂, 1 ♀, Makhedonia, Serrai, Strimonas delta, 28.VIII.1998 (cAss); 1 ♂, Thráki, Nomós Évros, Évros delta, Salicornia, 22.IV.1994, leg. Bense (cAss). Samos: see Tab. 2. Kos: 1 ♂, Tigaci, 18.IX.1989, leg. Jørum (cAss). CYPRUS: 1 ♂, Lemesos salt lake, 5 m, 9.III.1996, leg. Frisch (cAss). TURKEY: Mersin: 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Silifke, 1990, leg. Lödl (NHMW, cAss); 1 ♀, S Silifke, Göksu delta, 36°20'N, 34°01'E, 9.V.2004, leg. Brachat & Meybohm (cAss). Adana: 1 ♂, Ceyhan, Devécusta delta, 13–15.IV.1992, leg. Hovorka (cAss). Kayseri: 1 ♂, SW Şeyhşaban, 38°28'N, 35°18'E, 1150 m, 11.VI.1998, leg. Bartsch & Salmen (cAss). ISRAEL: 1 ♂, Dead Sea region, lake shore near Newe Zohar, 31°09'N, 35°22'E, -350 m, 27.II.2009, leg. Aßmann (cFel).

Comment: KOCH (1937) failed to specify any type material of *Lathrobium cycladicum*. It can be inferred from the specific epithet that the syntype(s) he based the description on originated from the Cyclades. Only one male syntype from Naxos was found in the Koch collection at NHMB. Nearly all of the abdomen and the aedeagus is missing. The latter was apparently mounted on a slide and separated from the specimen, most likely by H. Coiffait.

The original description of *L. biblicum* is based on a male and a female from “Atlith (südlich von Haifa, Palästina)”. In stating that he illustrated the aedeagus of the type in the caption of figure 10, KOCH (1937) designated the male as the holotype. The aedeagus of the examined holotype is missing, suggesting that it was lost or separated from the specimen either by C. Koch or by H. Coiffait. *Throbalium adanense* was described based on a unique male holotype from “Adana” (KOCH 1939). Very recently, BORDONI (2020) described *Throbalium kosianum* based on two males from the Aegean island Kos.

A comparison of the examined type material, of additional material from Greece (including Kos), Cyprus, Turkey, and Israel, and of the illustrations provided with the respective original descriptions revealed some intraspecific variation of the shapes of the male sternites VII and VIII (Figs 48–57), but yielded no evidence that *T. cycladicum*, *T. biblicum*, *T. adanense*, and *T. kosianum* should refer to different species. Similarly, no signifi-

cant differences were found in the structure of the aedeagus (Figs 40–47). However, there appears to be some clinal variation with the ventral process of the aedeagus tending to become broader towards the east of the distribution. In consequence, *T. cycladicum* is designated as the senior synonym of *T. biblicum*, which was described in the same article. *Throbalium adanense* and *T. kosianum* were made available subsequently and are thus junior synonyms of *T. cycladicum*.

Quedius cohaesus EPPELSHEIM, 1888

This species was listed as *Q. pseudonigriceps* REITTER, 1909 in ASSING (2017b). The name was recently synonymised with *Q. cohaesus* by ASSING (2019e).

Quedius hermonensis COIFFAIT, 1963

This species was listed as *Q. rugosipennis* FAGEL, 1969 in ASSING (2017b). The name was recently synonymised with *Q. hermonensis* by ASSING (2018c).

Quedius job COIFFAIT, 1963

The previously known distribution included Lesbos, Samos, Karpathos, South Turkey, and Lebanon (ASSING 2018c). Some paratypes of *Q. lydicus* FAGEL, 1968, a name recently synonymised with *Q. job* by ASSING (2018c), had been collected in Samos (FAGEL 1968). Additionally, the following material was examined from Samos: 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, Valeonates, Nightingale Valley, 37.784°N, 26.818°E, 70 m, stream bank, 9.VI.2013, leg. Degasperi (cDeg, cAss); 1 ex., Mili env., Imuresos, 5.IV.2008, leg. Rossi (cAss).

Quedius ortrudae KORGE, 1971

According to a recent revision (ASSING 2018c), this species was previously confounded with *Q. nivicola* KIESENWETTER, 1858, as which it was recorded from Samos by ASSING (2017b).

Quedius vicinus (MÉNÉTRIÉS, 1832)

The previously known distribution included Turkey, the Middle East, the Caucasus region, and Middle Asia (SCHÜLKE & SMETANA 2015). The material from Samos (and Rhodos; see the section on the Staphylinidae of Rhodos) represents the first records from the Aegean Islands (Samos, Rhodos) and Greece.

Descriptions of new species

Euphantias ambulans ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:4D363881-A549-4AA0-A824-66E2EBA02BD3

(Figs 3, 18–20)

Type material: Holotype ♀: “GREECE: Samos [35a], Psili Ammos, Alyki wetld, 37°42'31"N, 27°00'27"E, 5 m, salt meadow, 10.IV.2022, T. Forcke / Holotypus ♀ *Euphantias ambulans* sp. n., det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss). Paratype ♀: same data as holotype (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet is the present participle of the Latin verb *ambulare* (to walk) and alludes to the completely reduced hind wings.

Description: Body length 2.7–2.9 mm; length of fore-body 1.4–1.6 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 3. Colouration: body, including the appendages, blackish; whole body, including eyes, covered with dense, somewhat irregularly distributed pale scales.

Head (Figs 19–20) strongly domed in median dorsal portion, this elevation sharply delimited from (and by) lateral and posterior sulci; above antennal insertion strongly domed. Eyes large, strongly convex, and composed of coarse ommatidia, approximately three times as long as the distance between posterior margin of eye and posterior constriction of head in dorsal view. Antenna (Fig. 18) 1.0–1.1 mm long; antennomeres I large and long, approximately three times as long as broad, subapically constricted and apically somewhat flattened, covered with moderately dense scales not concealing all of integument, II much narrower and shorter than I and nearly twice as long as broad, III–IV of subequal length, very slender, strongly oblong, and longer and narrower than II, V of similar shape and II and III, but slightly longer, VI–VII much shorter than III–V, less slender, of conical shape, and approximately twice as long as broad, VIII of similar shape as VI–VII but slightly less oblong, IX significantly larger than VIII, of distinctly conical shape, and approximately as broad as long; X transverse, approximately 1.5 times as broad as long, and XI transverse and apically constricted.

Pronotum (Figs 19–20) 0.55–0.60 mm broad, 1.29–1.36 times as broad as long and 1.31–1.33 times as broad as head; middle of anterior margin, lateral and posterior margins strongly bulging; middle of disc with pair of pronounced oblong and narrowly separated elevations, area around these elevations deeply impressed.

Elytra (Figs 19–20) 1.17–1.19 times as long as pronotum, each elytron 1.55–1.60 times as long as broad and with a sutural, a humeral, and two intermediate carinae, all of them pronounced and reaching posterior margin of elytra (sutural and third carina), or nearly so (second and humeral carina); humeral carina most pronounced basally, gradually becoming less pronounced posteriad. Hind wings completely reduced.

Abdomen not distinctive.

♂: unknown.

Comparative notes: The enigmatic genus *Euphania* FAIRMAIRE & LABOULBÈNE, 1856 was previously represented in the Palearctic region by only four species, all of them extremely rarely found: *E. insignis* (MULSANT & REY, 1856) (North Africa: Algeria, Tunisia, Egypt; France, Italy; Middle East: Syria, Saudi Arabia) with the subspecies *E. insignis insularis* KOCH, 1934 endemic to Sardinia; *E. boiteli* NORMAND, 1936 (Tunisia); *E. pligin-skii* BERNHAUER, 1912 (Ukraine; Russian West Caucasus); *E. pusanovi* BLINSTEIN, 1976 (Ukraine). Using the key to species in BLINSTEIN (1976), *E. ambulans* would key out together with *E. pligin-skii* and *E. pusanovi*, mainly based on the longer antennomere I (*E. insignis* and *E. boiteli*: antennomere I only twice as long as broad). It is distinguished from *E. pligin-skii* and *E. pusanovi* as follows:

– from *E. pusanovi* by larger size (*E. pusanovi*: body length 2.2 mm), significantly larger eyes (*E. pusanovi*: eyes twice as long as postocular region), and much shorter median elevations of the pronotum (*E. pusanovi*: median elevations reaching anterior and posterior margins);
 – from *E. pligin-skii* by shorter elytra (*E. pligin-skii*: elytra > 1.25 times as long as pronotum; each elytron approximately 1.65 times as long as broad) with a less oblique humeral carina, more oblong and more distinctly separated median elevations of the pronotum, and longer and more slender antennomeres III–X.

For illustrations of *E. pusanovi* and *E. pligin-skii* see BLINSTEIN (1976) and <https://www.zin.ru/animalia/coleoptera/eng/euppligk.htm>.

Distribution and natural history: The type locality is situated near Psili Ammos, Southeast Samos. The specimens were hand-collected in a salt meadow near sealevel.

Hydrosmecta cultellata ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:014960F5-7A69-4D33-8B6F-2F543D07AF7D
 (Figs 5, 25–32)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GREECE: Samos [60], W Karlovassi, Potami, 37°47'11"N, 26°40'05"E, 30 m, stream bank, 16.IV.2022, V. Assing / Holotypus ♂ *Hydrosmecta cultellata* sp. n., det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss). Paratypes: 3 ♀ ♀: same data as holotype (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet is an adjective derived from the Latin noun *cultellum* (small knife). It alludes to the shape of the conspicuous process at the base of the ventral process of the aedeagus.

Description: Body length 2.5–2.8 mm; length of forebody 1.1–1.2 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 5. Colouration: body blackish; legs yellow; antennae blackish.

Head weakly transverse; punctation fine and moderately dense; interstices with shallow microsculpture. Eyes large, longer than distance from posterior margin of eye to posterior constriction of head in dorsal view. Antenna

0.8–0.9 mm long; antennomeres III–IV weakly oblong, V–X weakly oblong or as long as broad.

Pronotum 1.15–1.20 times as broad as long and approximately 1.1 times as broad as head; punctation and microsculpture similar to those of head; pubescence along midline directed anteriorly, posteriorly only near posterior margin.

Elytra slightly longer than pronotum; punctation extremely dense and fine, barely visible in the pronounced microsculpture even at high magnification (100 x).

Abdomen with dense and fine punctation; interstices with microsculpture.

♂: tergite VIII transverse, posterior margin weakly concave in the middle (Fig. 27); sternite VIII longer than tergite VIII, posterior margin strongly convex (Fig. 28); median lobe of aedeagus (Figs 29–30) 0.27 mm long and of very distinctive shape, at base of ventral process with additional knife-shaped process (best visible in lateral view).

♀: tergite VIII of similar shape as in male (Fig. 31); sternite VIII (Fig. 32) slightly longer than tergite VIII, posterior margin distinctly concave in the middle; spermatheca shaped as in Figs 25–26, with long apical cuticular invagination.

Comparative notes: This species is reliably distinguished from its congeners only by the shapes of the distinctive aedeagus and of the spermatheca.

Distribution and natural history: The type locality is situated near Potami Waterfalls to the west of Karlovassi, Northwest Samos. The specimens were floated from fine gravel on a stream bank at an altitude of 30 m.

On the species of the *Atheta* (*Philhygra*) *elongatula* group

In a comprehensive and, especially regarding the illustrations, superb revision of the *Atheta* subgenus *Hygroecia* MULSANT & REY, 1873, now a junior synonym of *Philhygra* MULSANT & REY, 1873, BRUNDIN (1944) described three subspecies of *Atheta elongatula* (GRAVENHORST, 1802), all of them currently regarded as distinct species: *Atheta cretica*, *A. balcanica* (a preoccupied name subsequently replaced with *A. balcanicola* SCHEERPELTZ, 1968), and *A. transcaspica* (today a junior synonym of *A. laevigata* (HOCHHUTH, 1849)). An additional species belonging to this group, *A. monstrosa*, was rather recently described by ASSING (2011). In external and the secondary sexual characters, the species of the *A. elongatula* group are highly similar, so that a reliable identification is possible only based on the shape of the aedeagus.

While *A. elongatula* is widespread in nearly all of the Palearctic region from West Europe in the west to East Siberia and North Korea in the east, the other species of this group have more restricted distributions, with *A. cretica* endemic to Crete, *A. balcanicola* distributed in

the Balkans and southern Central Europe, *A. monstrosa* recorded from North Turkey and Armenia, and the previously known distribution of *A. laevigata* ranging from the East Aegean Islands across Turkey to the Caucasus region.

Doubts regarding the identity of the specimens collected in Samos, together with the somewhat implausible distribution of *A. laevigata*, initiated a thorough revision of material previously identified as *A. cretica*, *A. balcanicola*, and *A. laevigata*. This study revealed that what had previously been recorded as *A. laevigata* from the Aegean Islands and South Turkey represented a distinct species distinguished from *A. laevigata* by slight, but constant differences in the shape of the aedeagus and also by external characters. This species is described below. Confirmed records of *A. laevigata* were seen only from the Caucasus region (Russian West Caucasus, Armenia, Northeast Turkey).

For an adequate assessment of the shape of the aedeagus, it should be noted that the large apical structure of the median lobe may be more or less extruded, thus sometimes conveying a misleading impression of aedeagal size and shape. Therefore, measurements of the aedeagus are always given as the length from the apex of the ventral process to the base of the aedeagal capsule.

For comparison, new illustrations of the aedeagi of *A. balcanicola*, *A. cretica*, *A. laevigata*, and *A. monstrosa* are provided in Figs 33–36.

Atheta (Philhygra) tecta ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2794087C-8BD2-4278-A358-D0CE8A62C1DB
(Figs 6, 37–39)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GR – Samothraki [16], W Lakkoma, 40°25'57"N, 25°30'54"E, 20 m, gravel river bank, 9.IV.2019, V. Assing / Holotypus ♂ *Atheta tecta* sp. n., det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss). Paratypes: 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀: same data as holotype (cAss); 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀: “GR – Samothraki [38a], SE Kamariotissa, 40°26'48"N, 25°29'53"E, 40 m, stream gravel, 16.IV.2019, V. Assing” (cAss); 1 ♂, 1 ♀: “GREECE: Samos [41], W Psili Ammos, 37°42'43"N, 26°59'06"E, 3 m, wetland, 10.IV.2022, T. Forcke” (cAss); 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀: same data, but “[41a] ... 11.IV.2022” (cAss); 1 ♀: “GREECE: Samos [50a], W Psili Ammos, 37°42'32"N, 26°59'20"E, 3 m, reed & salt meadow 13.IV.2022, T. Forcke” (cAss); 1 ♂: “GREECE: Samos [56], W Psili Ammos, 37°42'43"N, 26°59'18"E, 10 m, arable land, 13.IV.2022, T. Forcke” (cAss); 3 ♂♂, 1 ♀: “GREECE: Kos [14], 9.6 km WSW Kos, NW Zia, 36°50'58"N, 27°11'43"E, 210 m, leaf litter sifted, 26.XII.2016, V. Assing” (cAss); 13 ♂♂, 7 ♀♀: “TR. – Muğla; No. 13, SE Dalaman, 10 m, flood-plain wood, meadows, 36°47'02N, 28°50'03E, 28.III.2002, V. Assing” (cAss, MNB); 1 ♂: “N37°16' E028°10', Türkei Umg. Muğla, Bayir, 400 m, Meybohm 1.5.2001” (cAss); 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀: “TR [13a]– Konya, 35 km ENE Beyşehir,

E Hüyük, 37°56'38"N, 31°38'20"E, 1270 m, near reservoir, 20.IV.2011, V. Assing” (cAss, MNB); 2 ♂♂: “TR [12] – Tokat, 31 km ENE Tokat, Almuş, shore of reservoir, 40°23'N, 36°55'E, 810 m, 16.VII.2008, V. Assing” (cAss); 1 ♀: “TÜRKEI-S: Antalya 1997 Alara Han, 300 m, 20.3. leg. H. Winkelmann / *Atheta elongatula transcaucasica* det. J. Vogel, 1999” (MNB); 1 ♂: “TR [11], Antalya, Akdağlar 6 km S Kızılcadağ, 1455 m, 36°58'14"N, 29°58'05"E, Pappelhain, Laub+Mulm 16.II.2001, M. Schülke” (MNB).

Etymology: The specific epithet (Latin, adjective: hidden, secret) alludes to the fact that this species was previously confounded with *Atheta laevigata*.

Comment: The above type specimens from Kos and Samothraki were reported as *A. laevigata* by ASSING (2017a, 2019b).

Description: Body length 3.5–4.2 mm; length of forebody 1.5–1.8 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 6. Colouration: head black; pronotum dark-brown to black; elytra yellowish-brown to dark-brown; abdomen black, usually with the apex (segments IX–X and posterior portion of segment VIII) yellowish-brown to reddish-brown; legs yellow; antennae blackish-brown to black. Head and pronotum with fine, moderately dense punctation and with weak shine owing to very fine and shallow microsculpture. Other external characters not distinctive.

♂: sternite VIII longer than tergite VIII, posterior margin strongly convex; median lobe of aedeagus relatively small, 0.40–0.47 mm long, and shaped as in Figs 37–39.

Comparative notes: Regarding the shape of the aedeagus, *A. tecta* most resembles *A. cretica* and *A. laevigata*. The new species is distinguished from both species by a smaller and less robust body and by a smaller aedeagus with a smaller crista apicalis, an apically less strongly curved ventral process (lateral view), a ventro-apically more longer and more acute apical structure of the median lobe (lateral view), from *A. laevigata* additionally by paler colouration (especially of the elytra; *A. laevigata*: elytra usually black) and by a less matt forebody. For illustrations of the aedeagi of the other species of the *A. elongatula* group see Figs 33–36 and BRUNDIN (1944).

Distribution and natural history: The known distribution ranges from the East Aegean Islands (Samothraki, Samos, Kos) in the west across South Turkey (Muğla, Konya) northeastwards to Tokat. The specimens were collected on stream and river banks, on the shore of reservoirs, in wetlands and salt meadows, in a flood-plain forest, and on arable land. The altitudes range from near sealevel to 1270 m.

Cretotyphlus kerkisicus ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:16BD4F7A-B7A6-47B3-8025-342CAD1855EF

(Figs 7, 58–59)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GREECE: Samos [18], Oros Kerkis, NE-slope, 37°44'33"N, 26°39'28"E, 740 m, soil washing, 6.IV.2022, V. Assing / Holotypus ♂ *Cretotyphlus kerkisicus* sp. n. det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet is an adjective derived from Kerkis, the name of the mountain on whose north slope the holotype was collected.

Description: Body length 1.35 mm (abdomen extended), length of forebody approximately 0.6 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 7. Colour of body dark-yellowish.

Head with sparse, barely visible punctation and with very shallow microsculpture. Pronotum approximately as long as broad and slightly narrower than head; microsculpture slightly more distinct than that of head.

Abdomen with shallow microsculpture composed of large meshes; punctation extremely fine and moderately dense; posterior margin of tergite VIII truncate.

♂: sternite VIII (Fig. 59) nearly symmetric, weakly oblong, with unmodified chaetotaxy, and with a broadly concave posterior excision; aedeagus (Fig. 58) 0.28 mm long, weakly asymmetric; ventral process long, slender, and bisinuate, with a pronounced ventral tooth approximately in the middle.

♀: unknown.

Comparative notes: The genus *Cretotyphlus* ASSING, 2019 previously included three species, all of them locally endemic to Crete. Regarding the shape of the aedeagus, *C. kerkisicus* is very similar to *C. hamatus*, the type species of the genus. It differs from this species by a more slender and strongly bisinuate ventral process of the aedeagus and a slightly more oblong male sternite VIII with unmodified pubescence. For illustrations of *C. hamatus* see ASSING (2019d).

Distribution and natural history: Despite extensive soil sampling, *C. kerkisicus* was found in only one locality on the northeastern slope of Oros Kerkis, West Samos. The holotype was collected by washing soil from a dry stream valley with *Quercus ilex* and *Pinus* sp. at an altitude of 740 m.

Cephennium amplexans ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:41A5DF62-9FFC-44D3-A57C-20B2B93720B9

(Figs 10, 60)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GR Samos, Avlakia 100 m, N37°47' E26°51' / 28.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, aus Streu und Boden in Bachnähe / Holotypus ♂ *Cephennium amplexans* sp. n. det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss). Paratypes:

1 ♂: “GR Samos, Psili Amos 1 m, N37°42' E27°00' / 20.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, am Rand der Saline unter Mastix-Strauch” (cAss); 2 ♀♀: “GR Samos, Manolates 300 m, N37°47' E26°49' / 29.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, aus Streu und Boden unter Sträuchern” (cAss); 1 ♂: “GR Samos, Kosmadei 500 m, Höhle Tsitse Tripa, N37°45' E26°39' / 23.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, bei der Höhle” (cAss); 1 ♂: “GR Samos, Platanakia 100 m, N37°47' E26°50' / 29.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, Nachtigallental” (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet is the present participle of the Latin verb *amplexare* (to encompass, to embrace). It alludes to the shapes of the internal structures of the aedeagus, with one of the claw-shaped structures enveloping the other.

Description: Body length 0.8–1.0 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 10. Punctation of pronotum more distinct than that of elytra. Eye rudiments minute, composed of 2–4 ommatidia without pigmentation. Other external and male secondary sexual characters as in other species of the *C. unguicum* subgroup of the *C. corruptum* group.

♂: aedeagus (Fig. 60) approximately 0.23 mm long, broad, and apically weakly pointed in the middle; internal sac with a pair of strongly curved claw-shaped structures; parameres apically extending slightly beyond apex of median lobe.

Comparative notes: Based on the similar external characters and particularly the similarly derived structure of the aedeagus (internal sac with two claw-shaped structures), *C. amplexans* undoubtedly belongs to the *C. unguicum* subgroup of the *C. corruptum* group (see ASSING & MEYBOHM 2021a). Among the species of the *C. unguicum* subgroup, whose previously known representatives are all distributed in Southwest Turkey, the aedeagus of *C. amplexans* is most similar to that of *C. unguicum* ASSING & MEYBOHM (2021) from Dilek Dağı, a mountain in the Turkish province Aydın separated from the east coast of Samos only by the narrow Mycale Strait. However, in *C. unguicum*, the claw-shaped structures are of nearly identical shape and the left structure is much less strongly curved. For illustrations of the aedeagi of *C. unguicum* and other species of the *C. unguicum* subgroup see ASSING & MEYBOHM (2021a).

Based on the morphology of the aedeagus and external characters, *C. amplexans* is closely allied neither to any of the species known from mainland Greece (see ASSING & MEYBOHM 2021b), nor to those from Crete and Samothraki (ASSING 2019b, ASSING et al. 2019).

Distribution and natural history: The type material was found in several localities across Samos at altitudes of close to sea-level to 500 m. The specimens were sifted from litter and soil near a stream, near a salt-meadow, and near a cave.

Cephenium monstrans ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:86CB13EF-3F05-45A1-BB47-034707B226A5

(Figs 11, 61)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GR Samos, 430 m, 6 km westl. Pirgos, N37°43' E26°45' / 24.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, Bachtal, Kiefernwald / Holotypus ♂ *Cephenium monstrans* sp. n. det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss). Paratype ♂: “GR Samos, Platanakia 100 m, N37°47' E26°50' / 29.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, Nachtigalental” (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet is the present participle of the Latin verb monstrare (to show, to point). It alludes to the shapes of the internal structures of the aedeagus, both of which seem to point in the same direction.

Description: Body length 0.85–0.90 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 11. Punctuation of pronotum more distinct than that of elytra. Eye rudiments minute, composed of 2–3 ommatidia without pigmentation. Other external and male secondary sexual characters as in *C. amplexans* and other species of the *C. unguicum* subgroup.

♂: aedeagus (Fig. 61) approximately 0.23 mm long, broad, and apically truncate; internal sac with a pair of claw-shaped structures, both of them pointing to the left in ventral view.

Comparative notes: Like *C. amplexans*, *C. monstrans* belongs to the *C. unguicum* subgroup. It is reliably distinguished from *C. amplexans* and other species of the *C. unguicum* subgroup only based on the shapes of the internal structures of the aedeagus.

Distribution and natural history: The type material was found in two localities in Central and North Samos, in one of the localities together with *C. amplexans*. The specimens were sifted from litter and soil at altitudes of 100 and 430 m.

Stenichnus (Stenichnus) samius MEYBOHM spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:D281CE0D-EEA6-45E7-BCB2-21734004DD80

(Figs 14, 64)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GR Samos Potami 20 m N37°47' E26°40' / leg. 22.4.2003 Brachat & Meybohm im Schluchtwald / *Stenichnus samius* m. Meybohm 2022 det. / Holotypus” (cMey). Paratypes: 1 ♀: same data as holotype; 1 ♀: “GREECE: Samos [24a], W Karlovassi, Potami, 37°47'11"N 26°40'05"E, 30 m, litter sifted, 7.IV.2022, V. Assing” (cMey); 1 ♂: “N37°45'36 E26°40'55 GR Samos (13a) Kastania N 250 m leg. Brachat 4.4.2022” (cMey).

Etymology: The specific epithet (Latin, adjective) alludes to the fact that this species is most likely endemic to Samos.

Description: Body length ♂ 1.50–1.60 mm, ♀ 1.65–1.73 mm. Male habitus as in Fig. 14. Body weakly bicolored; head and pronotum brown, elytra black; legs, antennae, and palpi light brown.

Head strongly transverse, 1.3 times as broad as long, 0.8 times as broad as pronotum; head width 0.30 mm (♂) to 0.31 mm (♀), head length 0.23 mm (♂) to 0.24 mm (♀); postocular region as long as diameter of eyes; vertex and frons distinctly flattened, with punctures and pubescence dimorphic; punctures in female distinctly finer and sparser than in male; setae in female long, in male on vertex shorter and between eyes missing; supra-antennal tubercles very weakly pronounced. Eyes composed of approximately 20 ommatidia, in male slightly larger and with slightly more ommatidia than in female. Antenna slender, 0.85 mm (♂) to 0.90 mm (♀) long; antennomeres I–VII elongate, up to twice as long as broad, VIII about as long as broad, IX and X moderately transverse, XI distinctly shorter than the combined length of IX and X.

Pronotum weakly oblong, 0.41–0.42 mm long and 0.36–0.39 mm broad in male, 0.43 mm long and 0.39 mm broad in female; punctures very fine; pubescence very long and suberect; setae directed mediad in lateral portion of posterior half, otherwise directed posteriad; basally only with two minute pits separated from each other by half the distance as between pits and posterior margin.

Elytra broadly oval, dorsally flattened, 0.95–1.04 mm long and 0.68 mm broad in male, 1.06–1.10 mm long and 0.71–0.72 mm broad in female, broadest at anterior third, height approximately one-fourth of elytral length (lateral view); humeral angle and humeral fold absent; at base of each elytron with a large deep inner impression, lateral impressions absent; pubescence long and suberect, longest setae distinctly longer than combined length of antennomeres III–IV; punctuation on elytra distinct and moderately fine; elytral apices obliquely truncate. Legs relatively long and slender, with dilated femora; profemora with sexual dimorphism and more dilated than mesofemora, the latter more dilated than metafemora.

♂: profemur distally broadly dilated externally, forming an angle of approximately 135°; sternites III and V with a median impression, that of sternite III circular and shallow, that of sternite V transverse and deeper; aedeagus (Fig. 64) 0.29 mm long and 0.14 mm broad; sclerotised portion of dorsal aspect relatively long; dorsal plate distinctly longer than broad, apically emarginate; ventral plate much broader than dorsal plate, apically broadly truncate; lateral contours straight in dorsal view, only apex broadly rounded; parameres each with two apical setae.

Comparative notes: *Stenichnus samius* is most similar to *S. brachati* MEYBOHM, 2019 (Crete). Both species share broadly oval, dorsally weakly flattened elytra, broadly dilated male profemora forming an obtuse angle distally, and a similar aedeagus. *Stenichnus samius* is easily distinguished from *S. brachati* by larger body size, a bicolored body, and longer and more erect pubescence

of pronotum and elytra. The new species differs from *S. chius* MEYBOHM, 2016 (Chios), with which it shares a bicolored body and long suberect pubescence of the elytra, by broader and dorsally more flattened elytra, and from *S. lesbius* MEYBOHM, 2016 by smaller body size and denser and shorter pubescence of the elytra.

Distribution and natural history: *Stenichnus samius* is most likely endemic to Samos. The specimens were collected in northwestern Samos, three of them in the valley of Potami river by sifting litter of *Platanus*. The altitudes range from 20 to 250 m.

Stenichnus (Stenichnus) amphimykalicus MEYBOHM
spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:BC1B8722-6DC0-40C0-BC10-9A2E673C9E4E
(Figs 15, 65)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “Greece: Samos [16+1], Oros Kerkis: NW-slope, E Kalithea, 37°44'36"N 26°37'02"E, 580 m, 1.IV.2014, V. Assing / *Stenichnus amphimykalicus* m. Meybohm 2022 det. / Holotypus” (cMey). Paratypes 1 ♀: “N37°40'54 E027°10'03 (1) Türkiye Aydın Dilek Dagi Kanyon 70–370 m 16.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 2 ♂♂: “N37°40'19 E027°10'41 (2) Türkiye Aydın Dilek Dagi s Kanyon 670 m 17.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 1 ♀: “N37°40'56 E027°13'36 (25) Türkiye Aydın Dilek Dagi s Güzelcamli 440 m 26.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 1 ♀: “N37°41'29 E027°09'33 (26) Türkiye Aydın Dilek Dagi Kanyon 70–200 m 29.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 1 ♂: “N37°26'35 E028°18'07 (4) Türkiye Mugla Yatagan–Bozdogan 825 m 19.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 1 ♂: “N37°55'45 E027°53'46 (9) Türkiye Aydın Passayaylasi 1115 m 20.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 1 ♀: “TR [30] – Manisa, 10 km S Manisa, Karadağ, 1200 m, roadside, 38°33'26N 27°23'13E (26), 15.IV.2006 V. Assing” (cMey).

Etymology: The specific epithet (adjective) alludes to the fact that this species is distributed on both sides of the Strait of Mykali (the straight separating Samos from Turkey).

Description: Mean body length 1.29 mm. Male habitus as in Fig. 15. Body weakly bicolored; head and pronotum more or less distinctly dark-brown; elytra black; legs, antennae, and palpi pale-brown. Head strongly transverse, about 1.4 times as broad as long and 0.7 times as broad as pronotum; mean head width 0.26 mm, mean head length 0.19 mm; postocular region slightly longer than diameter of eyes; vertex and frons distinctly flattened, punctures and pubescence not dimorphic, punctures very fine and sparse, setae long; supra-antennal tubercles pronounced. Eyes composed of approximately 20 ommatidia, in male slightly larger and with slightly more ommatidia than in female.

Antenna on average 0.87 mm long; antennomeres I–VI elongate, III–VI up to 1.5 times as long as broad, VII about as long as broad, VIII moderately transverse, IX and X distinctly transverse, X about twice as broad as long, XI distinctly shorter than the combined length of IX and X.

Pronotum weakly transverse, on average 0.33 mm long and 0.36 mm broad, pubescence long and suberect; basally only with two minute pits separated from each other by the same distance as from posterior margin.

Elytra broadly oval, dorsally weakly flattened, on average 0.81 mm long and 0.52 mm broad, broadest at anterior third, height approximately one-third of elytral length (lateral view); humeral angles and humeral folds absent; at base of each elytron with a large deep inner impression, lateral impressions absent; pubescence long and suberect, longest setae about as long as combined length of antennomeres III and IV; punctuation on elytra distinct and moderately fine; elytral apices truncate. Legs relatively long and slender, with dilated femora; profemora with sexual dimorphism, more dilated than mesofemora, the latter more dilated than metafemora.

♂: profemur distally broadly dilated externally, forming an angle of approximately 120°; sternite IV and posterior portion of sternite V with a shallow median, more or less transverse impression; aedeagus (Fig. 65) on average 0.23 mm long and 0.13 mm broad; sclerotised portion of dorsal aspect relatively short; dorsal plate as long as broad, apically more or less emarginate; ventral plate much broader than dorsal plate, apically weakly convex; aedeagus in dorsal view rounded basally, constricted at apical third, apex broadly convex; parameres each with two apical setae.

Intraspecific variation: The specimens of Turkey differ from the holotype by slightly larger body size, slightly less erect and slightly shorter and denser pubescence of the elytra, and an apically slightly less emarginate dorsal plate of aedeagus. These differences, however, are insignificant and consequently interpreted as intraspecific variation.

Comparative notes: Based on the similar structure of the aedeagus and the modifications of the male sternites III–V, *S. amphimykalicus* belongs to a species group including *S. brachati* and *S. orientalis* MEYBOHM, 2019 from Crete, as well as *S. samius*, *S. chius*, and *S. lesbius* from the Aegean Islands. *Stenichnus amphimykalicus* additionally shares distally broadly dilated male profemora with *S. brachati*, *S. orientalis*, and *S. samius*. Of all these species, *S. amphimykalicus* is most similar to *S. brachati*, with which it also shares broadly oval, dorsally weakly flattened elytra and the male profemora forming an obtuse angle distally. The new species is distinguished from all the species of this species group by shorter antennae with antennomeres IX and X approximately twice as broad as long and by smaller body size (exception: *S. lesbius*).

Distribution and natural history: *Stenichnus amphimykalicus* is known from one locality in Samos and several localities in Aydın, Muğla, and Manisa provinces, South-west Turkey. The specimens were sifted from litter in various shrub and forest habitats at altitudes between 70 and 1200 m.

Scydmorephes amphimykalicus MEYBOHM spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:2CDA0C85-BA74-46EF-8AA6-ADAFB1974DC2

(Figs 16, 66)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “Greece: Samos [3], Oros Kerkis: Prof. Ilias, 37°43'34"N 26°38'02"E, 1210 m, sifted, 7.IV.2017, V. Assing / *Scydmorephes amphimykalicus* m. Meybohm 2022 det. / Holotypus” (cMey). Paratypes: 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀: same data as holotype (cMey); 1 ♀: “GR Samos Potami 20 m N37°47' E26°40' / leg. 22.4.2003 Brachat & Meybohm im Schluchtwald” (cMey); 1 ♂, 1 ♀: “Greece: Samos [16+1], Oros Kerkis: NW-slope, E Kalitheia, 37°44'36"N, 26°37'02"E, 580 m, 1.IV.2014, V. Assing” (cMey); 2 ♂♂: N37°44'35"E 26°37'02" GR Samos (14a) Kerkis Oros 600 m leg. Brachat 5.4.2022 (cMey); 2 ♂♂: “GR Samos Kosmadei 560 m N37°45' E26°39' / 1.5.2003 Brachat & Meybohm aus Farn und Boden am Platanenstumpf” (cMey); 1 ♂, 1 ♀: “GR Samos Kosmadei 600 m N37°44' E26°38' / 30.4.2003 Brachat & Meybohm vor dem Felspfad zur Höhle Kakoperato” (cMey); 1 ♀: “N37°40'19 E027°10'41 (2) Türkei Aydın Dilek Dagi s Kanyon 670 m 17.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀: “N37°41'26 E027°13'43 (24) Türkei Aydın Dilek Dagi s Güzelkamli 410 m 28.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey); 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀: “N37°40'56 E027°13'36 (25) Türkei Aydın Dilek Dagi s Güzelkamli 440 m 28.4.2006 l. Brachat & Meybohm” (cMey).

Etymology: The specific epithet (adjective) alludes to the fact that this species is distributed on both sides of the Strait of Mykali.

Description: Habitus as in Fig. 16. External characters as in *S. samothracicus* MEYBOHM, 2019 from Samothraki, except as follows:

Body larger, length 1.05–1.12 mm. Pubescence of elytra shorter, setae in basal third more erect and in apical half more bent downwards. Head width 0.21 mm in male and 0.20 mm in female, head length 0.16 mm. Eyes sexually dimorphic, in female much smaller than in male; female eyes composed of approximately 10 ommatidia and diameter of eyes about as long as antennomere V, distance between eyes about four times as long as diameter of eyes; male eyes composed of approximately 15 ommatidia and diameter of eyes about 1.5 times as long as antennomere V, distance between eyes about 2.5 times as long as diameter of eyes. Antenna longer (0.52 mm) and stouter; antennomeres II almost 1.5 times as long as broad, III as long as broad, IV and V slightly longer than broad, VI as long as broad, VII to X of increasing width, VIII to X about twice as broad as long. Pronotum 0.31 mm long and 0.27 mm

broad, broadest at anterior third, at base 0.24 mm broad and less contracted than in *S. samothracicus*. Elytra with slight sexual dimorphism, 0.68 mm long, 0.45 mm broad in female and 0.43 mm broad in male, broadest at anterior third, regularly convex, in dorsal view laterally more broadly rounded, in lateral view apically more convex.

♂: aedeagus (Fig. 66) with slightly convex apico-lateral parts; dorso-apical plate of internal sac more slender, broadened to base, laterally without concavity; small horseshoe-shaped plate situated dorsally of frond-shaped median sclerites indistinct; central projection of ventral border of ostium broader and laterally less emarginated.

Intraspecific variation: The specimens from Dilek Dağı differ from all except one of the specimens from Samos by slightly less curved setae on the elytra and by less distinctly broadened (dorsal view) and apically less convex (lateral view) elytra. The aedeagi, however, are identical.

Comparative notes: *Scydmorephes amphimykalicus* belongs to a group including numerous species distributed in the northern Mediterranean (from Spain to Turkey) and in Georgia. This group is mainly characterised by a pair of frond-shaped sclerites in the internal sac of the aedeagus and by a pronotum with carinate lateral margins only in the posterior half. *Scydmorephes amphimykalicus* is distinguished from all of them by the combination of characters indicated in the description above.

Distribution and natural history: This species is probably endemic to Samos and the geographically close Dilek Dağı in the Turkish province Aydın. The specimens were sifted from litter in various shrub and forest habitats at a wide range of altitudes (20 and 1210 m).

The Staphylinidae fauna of Ikaría

According to a checklist compiled in ASSING (2017b), 70 species of Staphylinidae were previously known from Ikaría, seven of them endemic.

Hydrosmecta insularum ASSING, 2019

The specimens recorded as *Hydrosmecta* sp. in ASSING (2017b) belong to *H. insularum* (see ASSING et al. 2019).

Oxypoda rectacia ASSING, 2019

According to a recent revision (ASSING 2019a), the material listed in ASSING (2017b) as *Oxypoda* cf. *nova* BERNHAUER, 1902 belongs to *O. rectacia*.

Description of new species

Cephennium icariae ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:738FF668-DCED-4E48-808C-0DE0D67797CA

(Figs 12, 62)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GR Ikaria, Steli 290 m, N37°35' E26°09' / 27.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, am grasigen Hang unter Gebüsch / Holotypus ♂ *Cephennium icariae* sp. n. det. V. Assing 2022” (cAss). Paratypes: 1 ♂: “GR – Ikaria, Steli, 290 m, N37°35'42" E26°9'44", 27.IV.2003, leg. Meybohm/Brachat” (cAss); 5 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀: “GR Ikaria, Nas 10–100 m, N37°37' E26°03' / 26.4.2003, leg. Brachat & Meybohm, im Bachtal aus Gras unter Mastix-Strauch” (cAss); 1 ♀: “GR – Ikaria, westl. Arministis, Nas, 290 m, N37°37'03" E26°03'46", 10–100 m, 26.IV.2003, leg. Meybohm/Brachat” (cAss); 1 ♀: “GREECE: Ikaría [7], S Evdilos, pass env., 37°35'20"N, 26°10'22"E, 570 m, sifted, 10.IV.2017, V. Assing” (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet is the genitive of Icaria, the island where this species is most likely endemic.

Description: Body length approximately 1.0 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 12. Punctuation of pronotum fine, only slightly more distinct than that of elytra. Eye rudiments minute, composed of 2–5 ommatidia without pigmentation.

♂: metaventrite flat, not impressed; aedeagus (Fig. 62) approximately 0.25 mm long, broad, and apically weakly convex; internal structure relatively large and symmetric, not claw-shaped; paramere apically extending slightly beyond apex of median lobe.

Comparative notes: Like the two species from Samos (*C. amplexans*, *C. monstrans*), *C. icariae* belongs to the *C. corruptum* group. It is reliably distinguished from other species of this group only by the shapes of the internal structures of the aedeagus. For illustrations of the aedeagi of the Turkish representatives of the *C. unguicum* subgroup see ASSING & MEYBOHM (2021a).

Distribution and natural history: The type material was found in three localities in Central Ikaría at altitudes between 10 and 570 m. The specimens were sifted from grass, litter, and roots in a grassy slope, in a stream valley, and at the margin of a pasture.

The Staphylinidae fauna of Samothraki

According to ASSING (2019b), the fauna of Samothraki was composed of at least 123 species, 114 of them named and six endemic. In the meantime, a revision of some of the material has revealed some misidentifications, one of them already published (ASSING 2020). The material previously identified as *Atheta laevi-*

gata now belongs to the type series of *A. tecta* (see the description of this species above). Other identification errors are rectified below. Including the additions, the fauna of Samothraki now includes at least 125 species, 116 of them named.

Aloconota eichhoffi (SCRIBA, 1868)

Two of the specimens reported as *Aloconota cambrica* (WOLLASTON, 1855) from localities 9 and 9a in ASSING (2019b) refer to *A. eichhoffi*.

Aloconota planifrons (WATERHOUSE, 1863)

One of the specimens reported as *Aloconota cambrica* from locality 12a in ASSING (2019b) belongs to *A. planifrons*.

Cypha spathulata ASSING, 2007

The record of *C. graeca* ASSING, 2004 in ASSING (2019b) in fact refers to *C. spathulata* (see ASSING 2020).

The Staphylinidae fauna of Lesbos

According to a recent study of the fauna of Lesbos (ASSING 2016b), 199 species, 184 named and 15 unnamed, had been recorded from this island. Nine of the named and at least two of the unnamed Pselaphinae and Scydmaeninae were considered endemics.

Hydrosmeeta insularum ASSING, 2019

The specimens recorded as *Hydrosmeeta* sp. 2 in ASSING (2016b) belong to *H. insularum* (see ASSING et al. 2019).

Myllaena graeca KRAATZ, 1858

A revision of some Mediterranean and Caucasian species of *Myllaena* ERICHSON, 1837 (ASSING 2018b) revealed that the specimen listed as *Myllaena* sp. in ASSING (2005) belongs to *Myllaena graeca*.

Pella discolor ASSING, 2008

The record of *Pella cinctipennis* (EPPELSHEIM, 1884) from Lesbos in ASSING (2016b) is based on misidentification. A revision of the material revealed that it belongs to *P. discolor*, the first record of this species from Greece and Europe.

Tab. 3: Updated checklist of the Staphylinidae recorded from Rhodos and results of the field trip conducted to Rhodos by Thomas Forcke in December 2019. Details on the localities/samples are provided at the end of the list. Specimen numbers are given in parentheses behind the sample number. First records from Rhodos are marked with an asterisk, first records from Greece with two, and first records from Europe with three asterisks. For additional footnotes and references for species recorded from Rhodos before 2013 see the footnotes and references in Assing (2013).

The references are abbreviated as follows: A13 = ASSING (2001); A17a = ASSING (2017a); A18a = ASSING (2018a); A19a = ASSING (2019a); A19c = ASSING (2019c); A21 = ASSING (2021); App = ASSING (present paper); M14 = MAKRANCZY (2014).

Species	Localities/samples	References
O m a l i i n a e		
<i>Aphaenostemmus rhodicus</i> ASSING, 2006		A13
<i>Dialycera aspera</i> (EPELSHEIM, 1889)		A13
<i>Omalium rhodicum</i> ZANETTI & ASSING, 2013		A13
<i>Omalium rivulare</i> (PAYKULL, 1789)		A13
<i>Omalium rugatum</i> MULSANT & REY, 1880		A13
P r o t e i n i n a e		
<i>Metopsia assingi</i> ZERCHE, 1998		A13
<i>Proteinus atomarius</i> ERICHSON, 1840		A13
<i>Proteinus utrarius</i> ASSING, 2004		A13
M i c r o p e p l i n a e		
<i>Micropeplus fulvus</i> ERICHSON, 1840		A13
<i>Micropeplus staphylinoides</i> (MARSHAM, 1802)		A13
P s e l a p h i n a e		
<i>Brachygluta cavernosa</i> (SAULCY, 1876)		A13
+ <i>Bryaxis</i> nov. sp.		A13
<i>Faronus distinctus</i> BESUCHET, 1999		A13
<i>Namunia myrmecophila</i> REITTER, 1884		A13, A17a
<i>Reichenbachia chevrieri</i> (AUBÉ, 1844)		A13
* <i>Rybaxis longicornis</i> (LEACH, 1817)	1(2), 1a(7), 1b(4), 1c(4)	App
*** <i>Sognorus calcaratus</i> (BAUDI DI SELVE, 1870)	5(1)	App
<i>Tribatus creticus</i> REITTER, 1884		A13
<i>Trimium libani</i> J. SAHLBERG, 1908		A13
<i>Tychus rhodensis</i> SABELLA et al., 1998		A13
T a c h y p o r i n a e		
<i>Lordithon thoracicus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1777)		A13
<i>Mycetoporus ignidorsum</i> EPELSHEIM, 1880	16(1)	A13, App
<i>Mycetoporus reichei</i> (PANDELLÉ, 1869)		A13
<i>Mycetoporus</i> cf. <i>simillimus</i> FAGEL, 1965		A13
<i>Parabolitobius inclinans</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)		A13
<i>Sepedophilus immaculatus</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)	13(1), 13a(1)	A13, App
* <i>Sepedophilus obtusus</i> (LUZE, 1902)	10b(1)	App
<i>Tachyporus abner</i> SAULCY, 1865	1a(1)	A13, App
<i>Tachyporus caucasicus</i> KOLENATI, 1846	10b(1)	A13, App
<i>Tachyporus hypnorum</i> (FABRICIUS, 1775)		A13
<i>Tachyporus nitidulus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1781)	1b(1), 2(1), 16(1)	A13, App

Species	Localities/samples	References
H a b r o c e r i n a e		
<i>Habrocerus cyprensis</i> ASSING & WUNDERLE, 1995		A13
<i>Habrocerus pisidicus</i> KORGE, 1971		A13
A l e o c h a r i n a e		
<i>Aleochara bipustulata</i> (LINNAEUS, 1760)		A13
<i>Aleochara laticornis</i> KRAATZ, 1856		A13
<i>Aleochara maculipennis</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1857		A13
<i>Aleochara tristis</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
<i>Alevonota libanotica</i> (FAGEL, 1965)		A13
* <i>Aloconota aegaea</i> ASSING, 2016		App
** <i>Aloconota pfefferi</i> (ROUBAL, 1929)		App
<i>Aloconota sulcifrons</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)		A13
<i>Atheta aegra</i> (HEER, 1841)		A13
<i>Atheta aeneicollis</i> (SHARP, 1869)	13(1)	A13, App
* <i>Atheta amicula</i> (STEPHENS, 1832)	1b(1)	App
<i>Atheta clientula</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)		A13
<i>Atheta coriaria</i> (KRAATZ, 1856)		A13
<i>Atheta longicornis</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
<i>Atheta meybohmi</i> ASSING, 2011		A13
<i>Atheta rhodiensis</i> SCHEERPELTZ, 1963		A13
<i>Atheta trinotata</i> (KRAATZ, 1856)		A13
<i>Atheta (Mocyta)</i> spp.	1(12), 1a(1), 1b(17), 1c(1), 2(2), 6(1), 7(2)	A13, App
<i>Cousya araxis</i> (BERNHAEUER, 1902)		[A13] ¹⁾ , A18a
<i>Cousya defecta</i> (MULANT & REY, 1875)		[A13] ¹⁾ , A18a
<i>Dinusa</i> sp. (♀)		A13
<i>Geostiba lucens</i> (BENICK, 1970)		A13
<i>Geostiba oertzeni</i> (EPPELSHEIM, 1888)		A13
<i>Geostiba rhodiensis</i> PACE, 1983		A13
<i>Liogluta longiuscula</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
<i>Myrmecopora fugax</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)		A13
<i>Myrmecopora laesa</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)		A13
+ <i>Myrmecopora rhodica</i> ASSING, 2013		A13
<i>Nehemitropia lividipennis</i> (MANNERHEIM, 1830)	1(1), 1b(1)	A13, App
<i>Oligota pusillima</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)		A13
<i>Oxypoda bimaculata</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1870	1b(1), 2(1), 7(3)	A13j, App
<i>Oxypoda exoleta</i> ERICHSON, 1839		A13
<i>Oxypoda lesbia</i> ASSING, 2005		A13
<i>Oxypoda obscuricollis</i> ASSING, 2007		A13
<i>Oxypoda rectacia</i> ASSING, 2019		[A13] ¹⁾ , A19a
<i>Oxypoda</i> sp.	1b(1)	App
<i>Parocyusa longitarsis</i> (ERICHSON, 1839)		A21
*** <i>Pseudosemiris atavia</i> ASSING, 2001	7(1)	App

Species	Localities/samples	References
O x y t e l i n a e		
<i>Anotylus clypeonitens</i> (PANDELLÉ, 1867)		A13
<i>Anotylus complanatus</i> (ERICHSON, 1839) (♀)		A13
<i>Anotylus inustus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)	2(1), 6(1)	A13, App
<i>Anotylus sculpturatus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)		A13
<i>Anotylus tetracarinated</i> (BLOCK, 1799)		A13
* <i>Bledius bedelianus</i> SCHÜLKE, spec. nov.		App
<i>Bledius bicornis</i> (GERMAR, 1823)		A13
<i>Bledius fossor</i> HEER, 1839		A17a
<i>Bledius spectabilis</i> (KRAATZ, 1857)		A13
<i>Bledius unicornis</i> (GERMAR, 1825)		A13
* <i>Bledius verres</i> ERICHSON, 1840	11(6)	App
*** <i>Carpelimus prudeki</i> GILDENKOV, 2013	1c(1)	App
<i>Ochtheophilus andalusiacus</i> (FAGEL, 1957)		M14
<i>Ochtheophilus venustus</i> (ROSENHAUER, 1856)		M14
* <i>Platystethus brevipennis</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1857	2(9), 6(3), 7(1)	App
<i>Platystethus nitens</i> (SAHLBERG, 1832)		A13
* <i>Platystethus spinosus</i> ERICHSON, 1840	7(10)	App
S t e n i n a e		
<i>Stenus aceris</i> STEPHENS, 1833	1(2), 1a(4), 1b(1), 1c(11)	A13, App
<i>Stenus assequens assequens</i> REY, 1884		A13
<i>Stenus brunnius lepidus</i> WEISE, 1875	6(1)	A13, App
<i>Stenus glacialis</i> HEER, 1839		A13
<i>Stenus guttula</i> MÜLLER, 1821	11(1), 16(2)	A13, App
<i>Stenus hospes</i> ERICHSON, 1840	2(1), 10b(1)	A13, App
<i>Stenus impressus</i> GERMAR, 1824		A13
<i>Stenus maculiger</i> WEISE, 1875		A13
<i>Stenus subaeneus</i> ERICHSON, 1840		A13
<i>Stenus turbulentus</i> BONDROIT, 1912	16(5)	A13, App
S c y d m a e n i n a e		
+ <i>Cephennium rhodicum</i> ASSING, nov. spec.		A13 ¹⁾ , App
+ <i>Euconnus dodecanicus</i> FRANZ, 1966		A13
+ <i>Euconnus oblitus</i> FRANZ, 1972		A13
+ <i>Euconnus rhodensis</i> FRANZ, 1966		A13
+ <i>Euconnus rhodicus</i> MEYBOHM, nov. spec.		A13
<i>Scydmaenus menozzii</i> FRANZ, 1966		A13
+ <i>Scydmorephes rhodensis</i> (FRANZ, 1966)		A13
L e p t o t y p h l i n a e		
+ <i>Kenotyphlus rhodiensis</i> COIFFAIT, 1973		A13
P a e d e r i n a e		
<i>Achenium debile</i> ERICHSON, 1840	1b(1), 2(3), 4(4), 6(5), 7(5)	A13, App
<i>Achenium picinum</i> FAUVEL, 1875		A13
* <i>Astenus bimaculatus bimaculatus</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)	7(2)	App

Species	Localities/samples	References
* <i>Astenus melanurus</i> (KÜSTER, 1853)	7(1)	App
<i>Astenus procerus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)		A13
<i>Astenus thoracicus</i> (BAUDI DI SELVE, 1857)	5(9), 7(6), 17(1)	A13, App
<i>Astenus rhodicus</i> ASSING, 2013.	10(1)	A13, App
<i>Domene stilicina</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)	1(1), 2(5), 5(1), 6(5), 7(21), 12(1)	A13, App
<i>Leptobium gracile</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	4(7)	A13, App
<i>Lobrathium rugipenne</i> (HOCHHUTH, 1851)	1(2), 10(1), 10b(9), 11(1), 14(2), 16(2), 19(1)	A13, App
<i>Medon dilutus pythonissa</i> (SAULCY, 1865)	1a(1), 15(1), 16(2)	A13, App
<i>Medon impar</i> ASSING, 2004		A13
<i>Medon lydicus</i> BORDONI, 1980		A13
<i>Medon maronitus</i> (SAULCY, 1865)		A13
<i>Medon semiobscurus</i> (FAUVEL, 1875)		A13
<i>Micranops pilicornis</i> (BAUDI DI SELVE, 1870)		A13
<i>Micrillus testaceus</i> (ERICHSON, 1840)	1b(1)	A13, App
* <i>Ochtheophilum turkestanicum</i> (KORGE, 1968)	1(3), 1a(1), 1b(34), 1c(13), 6(3)	App
<i>Pseudolathra quadricollis</i> (FAUVEL, 1875)	1b(3), 1c(1)	A19c, App
+ <i>Scopaeus schusteri</i> Scheerpeltz, 1965		A13
* <i>Scymbalium anale</i> (NORDMANN, 1837)	4(5)	App
+ <i>Sunius rhodicus</i> ASSING, 2013		A13
S t a p h y l i n i n a e		
<i>Bisnius fimetarius</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
<i>Bisnius sordidus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
<i>Dinothenarus flavocephalus</i> (GOEZE, 1777)		A13
* <i>Gabrius latro</i> JOY, 1913	1b(2)	App
* <i>Gabronthus maritimus</i> (MOTSCHULSKY, 1858)	1a(2), 1b(5), 1c(1)	App
* <i>Gauropterus fulgidus</i> (FABRICIUS, 1787)	3(9), 7(1)	App
* <i>Heterothops dissimilis</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	1a(1), 1c(1)	App
<i>Megalinus glabratus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
<i>Megalinus scutellaris</i> (FAUVEL, 1900)		A13
<i>Ocypus curtipennis</i> MOTSCHULSKY, 1849	5(1), 10(3), 10a(1), 13a(1), 20(16)	A13, App
<i>Ocypus mus</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	1(1), 10(7), 10a(1), 13(3), 13a(12), 15(14), 18(2), 20(1)	A13, App
<i>Ocypus orientis</i> SMETANA & DAVIES, 2000	3(1), 4(1), 5(3), 6(2)	A13, App
<i>Othius laeviusculus</i> STEPHENS, 1833		A13
<i>Othius lapidicola</i> MÄRKEL & KIESENWETTER, 1848	(15(3), 16(1))	A13, App
<i>Phacophallus parumpunctatus</i> (GYLLENHAL, 1827)		A13
<i>Philonthus concinnus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)	1(1), 1b(1), 1c(2)	A13, App
<i>Philonthus cruentatus</i> (GMELIN, 1790)		A13
<i>Philonthus ebeninus</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1802)		A13
* <i>Philonthus juvenilis</i> PEYRON, 1858	14(1)	App
* <i>Philonthus rufimanus rufimanus</i> ERICHSON, 1840	11(2)	App

Species	Localities/samples	References
<i>Quedius acuminatus phenicius</i> COIFFAIT, 1967		A13
<i>Quedius cinctus</i> (PAYKULL, 1790)		A13
<i>Quedius fissus</i> GRIDELLI, 1938	15(5)	A13, App
<i>Quedius humeralis</i> STEPHENS, 1832		A13
<i>Quedius lateralis</i> GRAVENHORST, 1802		A13
<i>Quedius levicollis</i> (BRULLÉ, 1832)	15(46)	A13, App
<i>Quedius nemoralis</i> BAUDI DI SELVE, 1848	15(30), 16(6)	A13, App
* <i>Quedius nitipennis</i> (STEPHENS, 1833)	10(1), 10b(5),	App
* <i>Quedius ortrudae</i> KORGE, 1971	1a(1)	App
<i>Quedius scintillans</i> (GRAVENHORST, 1806)	7(1), 10b(1), 16(1)	A13, App
<i>Quedius semiobscurus</i> (MARSHAM, 1802)	15(60)	A13, App
* <i>Quedius suturalis</i> KIESENWETTER, 1845	16(1)	App
** <i>Quedius vicinus</i> (MÉNÉTRIÉS, 1832)	1(1), 1a(2), 1b(1), 4(1), 6(4)	App
* <i>Stenistoderus cephalotes</i> (KRAATZ, 1858)	1b(3), 4(5)	App
<i>Xantholinus rufipennis</i> ERICHSON, 1839	1c(1), 6(1), 7(3)	A13, App
<i>Xantholinus varnensis</i> COIFFAIT, 1972	1(2), 1a(1), 1b(1), 1c(1), 2(3), 6(1), 7(17)	A13, App

Footnote: ¹⁾ listed as unnamed species in ASSING (2013).

Cafius pruinosus (ERICHSON, 1840)

ASSING (2016b) recorded *Remus sericeus* HOLME, 1837 from Lesbos. A revision of the material revealed that it in fact belongs to *Cafius pruinosus*, a species recently moved from *Remus* HOLME, 1837 to *Cafius* STEPHENS, 1829 by Yoo et al. (2021).

The Staphylinidae fauna of Rhodos

According to a first comprehensive account, including an annotated checklist, the Staphylinidae fauna of Rhodos was composed of at least 130 species, with thirteen (three undescribed) of them endemic. In the meantime, several additional species have been reported (ASSING 2017a, 2019c, 2021, MAKRANCZY 2014), some previously unnamed species have been revised (Assing 2018a, 2019a), and two species previously assumed to be endemic (*Omalium rhodicum*, *Astenus rhodicus*) have been shown to be more widespread.

Thomas Forcke (Hannover) conducted a field trip to Rhodos from 22 December 2019 to 1 January 2020, primarily aiming at collecting Carabidae. The staphylinid by-catches totalled 341 specimens belonging to 42 species, with as many as 18 of them recorded from Rhodos and five from Greece for the first time.

David Wrase (Gusow-Platow), too, collected Carabidae in Rhodos in May, 2015, and forwarded the Staphylinidae (276 specimens of 21 species, four of them unidentified, six of them first records from Rhodos) to Michael Schülke.

Including all the changes and additions, the staphylinid fauna of Rhodos is now composed of 160 identified named species (plus several unidentified and unnamed species), ten of which are currently known only from Rhodos and probably endemic.

In view of the number of additions and changes, an updated checklist is provided in Tab. 3.

Localities/samples: 22 December 2019 – 1 January 2020, leg. Forcke (sample numbers 1–9): **1:** 2 km S Haraki, 36°08'58"N, 28°04'47"E, 4 m, beach, under debris and stones, 22.XII.2019; **1a:** same data, but under debris, 27.XII.2019; **1b:** same data, but debris sifted, 28.XII.2019; **1c:** same data, but debris sifted, 1.I.2020; **2:** 3 km SW Apolakkia, mouth of Kourkourtahi, 36°03'03"N, 27°45'35"E, 3 m, arable land near beach, under debris and stones, 24.XII.2019; **3:** northern part of Apolakkia dam, 36°06'47"N, 27°47'37"E, 105 m, wetland, under debris and stones, 25.XII.2019; **4:** NW Siana, Akramitis north side, 36°09'58"N, 27°45'43"E, 290 m, partly flooded arable land, under stones and debris, 25.XII.2019; **5:** NW Siana, Akramitis north side, 36°09'49"N, 27°44'27"E, 270 m, grassy area, under stones, 26.XII.2019; **6:** 3 km N Apolakkia, 36°05'37"N, 27°47'53"E, 80 m, arable land, under stones, 29.XII.2019; **7:** S Kissamos, Limni, 35°22'15"N, 23°37'55"E, 570 m, margin of artificial pond with old *Platanus orientalis*, litter sifted, 22.XII.2019; **8:** NE Kandanos, Spina, 35°21'43"N, 23°46'51"E, 710 m, stream valley with oak, *Platanus orientalis*, other trees, and fern undergrowth, soil washing, 22.XII.2019; **9:** 1 km N Apolakkia, 36°04'25"N, 27°47'24"E, 50 m, partly flooded arable land, under stones and debris, 31.XII.2019.

14–20 May, 2020, leg. Wrase & Laser (sample numbers 10–20): **10**: ca 1 km SE Ialysos, 36°24'09"N, 28°09'19"E, 30 m, grassland with olive trees, under stones, 14–19.V.2015; **10a**: same data, but pitfall traps with vinegar, 19–20.V.2015; **10b**: ca 1 km SE Ialysos, 36°24'09"N, 28°09'19"E, 20 m, stream, under vegetation and stones, 20.V.2015; **11**: W Kolymbia, Loutanis river at Epta Piges (Seven Springs), 36°15'34"N, 28°06'34"E, 80 m, river bank, in gravel, 15&19.V.2015; **12**: ca 3.5 km SW Archangelos, 36°12'00"N, 28°03'59", 20 m, loamy field margin, under vegetation, 15.V.2015; **13**: W Kolymbia, forest near Epta Piges, 36.04'08"N, 28°04'30"E, 90 m, nearly dry streambed, under stones, 16.V.2015; **13a**: same data, but pitfall traps with vinegar; **14**: NW Kiotari, Asklipinos river, near bridge, 36°04'01"N, 27°55'44"E, 60 m, river bank with gravel and mud, 16.V.2015; **15**: Profitis Ilias, 36°16'25"N, 27°55'44", 690 m, pine forest, under stones and sifted from litter and moss, 17.V.2015; **16**: ca 1.2 km SE Eleoussa, 36°16'14"N, 28°02'36"E, 200 m, bank of small stream with gravel, 17.V.2015; **17**: 2.8 km W Ghadura Reservoir, 2.8 km SW Masari, 36°09'45"N, 28°03'E, 30 m, loamy wetland, 19.V.2015; **18**: Petaloudes (Butterfly Valley), 36°12'16"N, 28°03'45"E, 230 m, forest, under stones along path, 20.V.2015; **19**: W Ancient Kamiros, 36°20'09"N, 27°56'27"E, 5 m, gravel bank of small stream, 20.V.2015; **20**: 3 km S Ródos, Princess Flora Hotel, 36°24'34"N, 28°13'29"E, 20 m, around buildings, collected at night, 14–20.V.2015.

Notes on some species

Sognorus calcaratus (BAUDI DI SELVE, 1870)

According to SCHÜLKE & SMETANA (2015), this species had been recorded only from Turkey and Cyprus. The specimen listed in Tab. 3 represents the first records from Rhodos, Greece, and Europe.

Pseudosemiris atavia ASSING, 2001

Only three specimens from the Turkish provinces Mersin and Osmaniye were known previously (ASSING 2001, 2004). The male listed in Tab. 3 represents the first records from Rhodos, Greece, and Europe.

Carpelimus prudeki GILDENKOV, 2013

The original description is based on type material from the environs of Silifke in the Turkish province Mersin (GILDENKOV 2013). The male listed in Tab. 3, which was identified by Mikhail Gildenkov based on a photograph of the aedeagus, represents the first records from Rhodos, Greece, and Europe.

Quedius vicinus (MÉNÉTRIÉS, 1832)

The previously known distribution included Turkey, the Middle East, the Caucasus region, and Middle Asia (SCHÜLKE & SMETANA 2015). The material from Rhodos (and Samos; see the section on the Staphylinidae of Samos) represents the first records from the Aegean Islands (Rhodos, Samos) and Greece.

Additional records

Aloconota aegaea ASSING, 2016

Material examined: Rhodos: 1 ex., 5 km W Kolimbia, 14.V.2013, leg. Ziegler (cAss).

This species was previously known only from Samos, Lesbos, and Samothraki. The above specimen represents the first record from Rhodos.

Aloconota pfefferi (ROUBAL, 1929)

Material examined: Rhodos: 1 ex., 5 km W Kolimbia, 14.V.2013, leg. Ziegler (cAss).

This species was previously known from Central Europe, Italy, the northern Balkans, and Ukraine (SCHÜLKE & SMETANA 2015). The above specimen represents the first record from Rhodos and Greece.

Parocyusa longitarsis (ERICHSON, 1839)

Material examined: Rhodos: 1 ex., Loutani, above Epta Piges, 7–19.IV.1995, leg. Zwick (cAss); 1 ex., 5 km W Kolimbia, 14.V.2013, leg. Ziegler (cAss); 1 ex., N Apolakkia, reservoir, 36°05'49"N, 27°47'29"E, 90 m, 9.IV.2007, leg. Bahr et al. (MNB).

The first two specimens listed above were already reported from Rhodos without specified localities by ASSING (2021).

Descriptions of new species

Cephennium rhodicum ASSING spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:63142283-CD20-46E9-AB60-9F7AFA6DE29A
(Figs 13, 63)

Type material: Holotype ♂: "GR Rhodos 300 m, Eleousa Ag. Nikolaos, Fountoukli, Meybohm 10.4.1999 / Holotypus ♂ *Cephennium rhodicum* sp. n. det. V. Assing 2022" (cAss). Paratypes: 1 ♂, 6 ♀ ♀: same data as holotype; 1 ♂: same data as holotype, but 9.4.1999 (cAss); 1 ♀: "GR Rhodos (6), Epta Piges 70 m, N36°15'22 E28°06'50,

leg. Meybohm 3.4.2012" (cAss); 1 ♂: "GR Rhodos 320 m (2), Ag. Nikolaos Fontoukli, N36°16'27 E27°59'51, leg. Meybohm 3.4.2012" (cAss); 1 ♂: "GR Rhodos 500 m, Salakos Prof. Ilias, östl. Hotels, Meybohm 9.4.1999" (cAss); 1 ♀: "GREECE – Rhodos [4], 5 km SW Embonas, Attaviros, 36°11'59"N, 27°48'56"E, 580 m, 17.III.2013, V. Assing" (cAss).

Etymology: The specific epithet (Latin, adjective) alludes to the distribution of this species, which is most likely confined to Rhodos.

Description: Body length approximately 1.0 mm. Habitus as in Fig. 13. Punctuation of pronotum significantly denser and more distinct than that of elytra. Eye rudiments minute, composed of 3–5 ommatidia without pigmentation.

♂: aedeagus (Fig. 63) approximately 0.25 mm long, broad, and apically weakly, obtusely pointed in the middle; internal structure relatively large and symmetric, not claw-shaped; paramere apically extending to apex of median lobe.

Comparative notes: Based on the structure of the aedeagus and external characters, *C. rhodicum* belongs to the *C. corruptum* group, whose representatives are distributed in the region from Samos and Ikaría across South Turkey to the Middle East (Lebanon, Jordan) (ASSING & MEYBOHM 2021a) and from which *C. rhodicum* is reliably distinguished only by the shapes of the internal structures of the aedeagus. For illustrations of the aedeagi of the previously described representatives of the *C. corruptum* group see ASSING & MEYBOHM (2021a).

Distribution and natural history: The known distribution is confined to several localities in Rhodos. The specimens were found at altitudes of 70–580 m. The specimen from Attaviros was sifted from litter in a pine forest.

Euconnus (Tetramelus) rhodicus MEYBOHM spec. nov.

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:A286F3E4-9AC8-434F-B473-96E388B238A8

(Figs 17, 67)

Type material: Holotype ♂: "Greece: Rhodos [12], N Monolithos, Akramitis, 36°09'56"N, 27°45'43"E, 300 m, pine forest, sifted 21.III.2013, V. Assing / *Euc. (Tetramelus) rhodicus* m. Meybohm 2022 det. / Holotypus" (cMey). Paratype: 1 ♀: same data as holotype (cMey).

Etymology: The specific epithet (Latin, adjective) alludes to the hypothesis that this species is probably endemic to Rhodos.

Description: Habitus as in Fig. 17. Body length 1.77 mm (♂) and 1.85 mm (♀). Head approximately 0.28 mm broad, 1.18 times as long as broad, postero-medially bulging and projecting beyond posterior constriction.

Eyes with three ommatidia, weakly pigmented in male and without pigmentation in female. Antenna 0.80 mm (♂) and 0.85 mm (♀) long; antennomeres II twice as long as broad, III–VI cylindrical and about 1.5 times as long as broad, VII intermediate between VI and VIII, VIII–X nearly as broad as long, and XI distinctly shorter than the combined length of IX and X. Pronotum nearly 1.15 times as long as broad. Elytra 1.6 times (♂) and 1.5 times (♀) as long as broad. Legs slender, mesotibiae 0.42 mm long. ♂: metasternum with long, broad, and deep median impression; mesotrochanter unmodified; aedeagus (Fig. 67) slender, 0.54 mm long; ventral process (dorsal view) nearly straight and only indistinctly tapering from base, on either side of middle without a series of microsetae; the two large sclerites slender, almost symmetrically and evenly curved and converging, without teeth; dorsal plate apically broadly truncate, and with large emargination, lateral wing-shaped structures large, distinctly projecting from lateral contours of capsule; parameres with three apical setae.

Comparative notes: *Euconnus rhodicus* is distinguished from the similar *E. kerkisicus* from Samos by slightly larger body size, slightly longer and especially more slender antennae with antennomeres VIII–X not broader than long, longer tibiae, a large impression on the male metasternum, and unmodified male mesotrochanters. The aedeagus differs from that of *E. kerkisicus* especially by its more slender shape, a large emargination of the dorsal plate, and large, slender, and almost symmetric internal sclerites.

Distribution and natural history: This species is most likely endemic to Rhodos. The specimens were sifted from litter in a pine forest with undergrowth at an altitude of 300 m.

On two Mediterranean *Bledius* species (authored by Michael Schülke)

Bledius (Hesperophilus) bedeli FAUVEL, 1878

(Fig. 8)

Type material examined: Syntypes: 1 ♀: "Daya [round, violet] / Fauvel [round, red] / Bedeli Daya (Algerie) / P. de Borre / SYNTYPUS- ♀ *Bledius bedeli* Fauvel, 1878 det. M. Schülke 2011" (MHNG); 1 ♀: "Daya / Spec. typ. / J. Sahlb. / 9. / *Bedeli* Fvl. Alg. typ. / D.E.I. Coll. von Heyden / DEI Müncheberg Col-02277 [light green]" (SDEI); 1 ♀: "*Bedeli* Fauv. Daya, Oran Bedel typ. / D.E.I. coll. von Heyden / *Bledius Bedeli* Fauv. / DEI Müncheberg Col-02276 [light green]" (SDEI); 1 ex.: "Daya / *Bedeli* Fauv. / Coll. R. I. Sc. N. B." (IRSNB); 1 ♀: "Daya (Algerie) / *Bedeli* / Fauvel Type / Coll. R. I. Sc. N. B." (IRSNB); 4 exs. [without locality data, but mounted on identical mounting cards]: "Coll. R. I. Sc. N. B." (IRSNB).

Figs 1–13: Habitus of *Paramaurops creticus* (1), *Afropselaphus chanianus* (2), *Euphantias ambulans* (3), *Liogluta aloconotoides*, holotype (4), *Hydrosmecta cultellata* (5), *Atheta tecta* (6), *Cretotyphlus kerkisicus* (7), *Bledius bedeli* (8), *B. bedelianus* (9), *Cephennium amplexans* (10), *C. monstrans* (11), *C. icariae* (12), and *C. rhodicum* (13). Scale bars: 1.0 mm.

Figs 14–26: *Stenichnus samius* (14), *S. amphimykalicus* (15), *Scydmoraphes amphimykalicus* (16), *Euconnus rhodicus* (17), *Euphania ambulans* (18–20), *Paramaurops creticus* (21), *Afropselaphus chanianus* (22), *Cephennium idanum* from Selena Oros (23), *Liogluta aloconotooides*, holotype (24), and *Hydrosmecta cultellata* (25–26): 14–17 – habitus; 18 – antenna; 19 – forebody in dorsal view; 20 – forebody in lateral view; 21–23 – aedeagus; 24–26 – spermatheca. Scale bars: 14–17: 1.0 mm; 18–20: 0.5 mm; 21–26: 0.1 mm.

Figs 27–39: *Hydrosmecta cultellata* (27–32), *Atheta laevigata*, Armenia (33), *A. cretica* (34), *A. monstruosa*, Armenia (35), *A. balcanicola*, Pelopónnisos (36), and *A. tecta* (37–39; 37: holotype; 38: Samos; 39: Kos): 27 – male tergite VIII; 28 – male sternite VIII; 29–30, 33–39 – median lobe of aedeagus; 31 – female tergite VIII; 32 – female sternite VIII. Scale bars: 27–28, 31–39: 0.2 mm; 29–30: 0.1 mm.

Figs 40–57: *Throbalium cycladicum* (40–41, 50–52: mainland Greece; 42, 48–49, 53: Samos; 43: Kos; 44, 54: Cyprus; 45, 56: Turkey: Adana; 46: holotype of *T. adanense*; 47, 57: Israel; 55: Turkey: Kayseri): 40–47 – aedeagus in ventral view; 48 – male sternite VII; 49 – male sternite VIII; 50–57 – postero-median portion of male sternite VII. Scale bars: 0.2 mm.

Figs 58–67: *Cretotyphlus kerkisicus* (58–59), *Cephennium amplexans* (60), *C. monstrans* (61), *C. icariae* (62), *C. rhodicum* (63), *Stenichnus samius* (64), *S. amphimykalicus* (65), *Scydmoraphes amphimykalicus* (66), and *Euconnus rhodicus* (67): 58, 60–67 – aedeagus; 59 – male sternite VIII. Scale bars: 0.1 mm.

Figs 68–71: *Bledius bedelianus*: 68–69 – aedeagus in ventral view (68: Israel; 69: Turkey: Antalya); 70–71 – male sternite VII (70: Antalya; 71: Israel). Scale bars: 70–71: 0.5 mm; 68–69: 0.2 mm.

Additional material examined: ALGERIA: 1 ex., “Hussein-Dey, plage prés polygone” (IRSNB); 2 exs. [without labels but mounted on identical mounting cards] (IRSNB); 2 exs., Tlemcen env., 1932, leg. Lebrousse (IRSNB).

Distribution: *Bledius bedeli* was originally described from Algeria (FAUVEL 1878) and subsequently recorded from Morocco by KOCHER (1958), as well as from Lebanon and Turkey by HERMAN (1986). A revision of the material recorded by HERMAN (1986) revealed that the records from Lebanon and Turkey are based on misidentification and refer to an undescribed species (see material of *B. bedelianus* below). The known distribution of the species is restricted to North Africa. The habitus of a syntype from Daya is shown in Fig. 8.

Bledius (Hesperophilus) bedelianus SCHÜLKE spec. nov.
 urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:84848C14-D6BD-41DF-9D76-EFDDC83FE7CD
 (Figs 9, 68–71)

Type material: Holotype ♂: “GREECE, Rhodos Lindos Saidouras river 18.04.1994 leg. J. Frisch / Holotypus *Bledius (Hesperophilus) bedelianus* spec. nov. det. M. Schülke 2011 [red]” (MNB). Paratypes: 26 exs.: same data as the holotype (MNB); 1 ex.: “GR Rhodos, Kolimbia, Strand, 36°15'17"N 28°10'06"E, 06.04.2007, leg. Bahr, Bayer, Brunner & Winkelmann (FO15)” (MNB); 5 exs.: “GREECE, Karpathos Aperi, 300 m NN 25.IV.1994, leg. J. Frisch” (MNB); 1 ex.: “GREECE, Karpathos Pigadia 10 m NN 22.IV.1994, leg. J. Frisch” (MNB); 1 ex.: “GREECE (Dodecanissa) Ródos, 2.8 km W Ghadura Reservoir, 2.8 km SW Masari, N36°09'44.6"/E 28°03' (loamy wet area) 32 m, 19.V.2015, Wrase & Laser [12]” (MNB); 3 exs.: “GREECE: Samos [23a] E Karlovassi, 37°47'14"N, 26°43'46"E, 40 m, river

bank, 14.IV.2022, T. Forke” (cAss); 2 exs.: same data, but “[23b], 16.IV.2022, leg. Assing & Forcke” (cAss); 9 exs.: “GREECE: Samos [49], E Myli, 37°40'39"N, 26°52'19"E, 15 m, river bank, 12.IV.2022, T. Forke” (cAss); 1 ex.: “GREECE: Samos [60], W Karlovassi, Potami, 37°47'11"N, 26°40'05"E, 30 m, stream bank, 16.IV.2022, V. Assing” (cAss); 1 ♂: “ISRAEL, (Centr. distr.) N Tel Aviv, Breikhat Ya'ar wetland 28.III.2008, leg. T. Aßmann” (MNB); 2 exs.: “Liban: Nahr el Kelb V. 1964 G. Fagel / G. Fagel sp. apud. *bedeli* Fauv. / [green round label] / Coll. R. I. Sc. N. B.” (IRSNB); 1 ex.: “Beirut / U. Sahlb. / 2322 / *Bledius bedeli* Fvl.” (IRSNB); 1 ex.: “Turkey, Anatolia mer. Mersin; Kurtulus nr. Silifke, 12.–17.V.1994, leg. Prudek” (MNB); 16 exs.: “TURKEY: nr. Antalya Ihsaniye, 07.v.2001, 200 m 36°55'08"N 30°49'42"E ex flooded pasture, MLV Barclay & D J Mann” (BMNH, MNB); 28 exs.: “TURKEY: Antalya Dist. Ihsaniye, 13.v.2001, 36°55'08"N 30°49'42"E 200 m, ex flooded pasture, MLV Barclay & D J Mann” (BMNH, MNB); 1 ex.: “Turquie: Cilicia Adana S. Breuning / G. Fagel sp. apud. *bedeli* Fauv. / [green round label] / Coll. R. I. Sc. N. B.” (IRSNB); 1 ex.: “Zypern–N. GIRNE/KYRENIA. 3.–17.4.1992, leg. Winkelmann-Klöß” (MNB).

Etymology: The specific epithet is derived from the name of the similar *B. bedeli*.

Description: Habitus as in Fig. 9. Size similar to that of *B. gallicus* (GRAVENHORST, 1806), body length 4.50 to 5.55 mm, length of forebody 2.40 to 2.85 mm. Head and pronotum blackish; elytra pale-brown to dark-brown, sometimes slightly darkened along suture; abdomen pitchy-brown to blackish, with posterior segments from apex of segment VII somewhat paler; antennae yellowish, with the apical antennomeres sometimes slightly darker; legs yellowish to pale brown.

Head moderately large, approximately 0.95 mm broad (between eyes approximately 0.65 mm). Eyes short (eye length 0.23 mm) and distinctly protruding. Surface of head dull, with distinct microsculpture, setiferous punctation very indistinct, rough, and shallow. Labrum moderately transverse, with distinct microsculpture and two small and round tubercles at apical margin. Mandibles tridentate in male and bidentate in female. Antenna of male elongated, antennomeres IV to VI slightly longer than broad, VII to X as long as broad; antenna of female slightly shorter, penultimate antennomeres as long as wide or weakly transverse.

Pronotum bulging, slightly transverse, approximately 1.2 times as broad as long, midlongitudinal sulcus short, obsolete especially in anterior portion; explanate margins entirely visible in dorsal view; posterior angles obsolete; protergosternal suture present, procoxal fissure closed; dorsal surface with weak shine; microsculpture distinct, less fine than that of head; setiferous punctation distinct, of similar density, but much deeper than that of head.

Elytra moderately short, as wide as pronotum and weakly transverse (length from humeral angles/width 0.90–0.99), slightly extended backwards; epipleural ridge complete; posterior margin with small membranous lobe; surface glossy, without visible microsculpture; setiferous punctation finer and denser than that of the pronotum. Protibia with two rows of spine-like setae; tarsal formula 4-4-4.

Abdomen with distinct transverse microsculpture, meshes short in anterior tergal impressions, much more transverse in posterior tergal portions. Setiferous punctation inconspicuous, of similar density as that of the elytra, but finer; posterior margin margin of tergite VIII emarginate.

♂: posterior margin of sternite VII (Figs 70–71) almost completely rounded, with shallow membranous emargination in the middle of the posterior margin (membranous emargination mostly indistinct in specimens from Greek islands, more distinct in specimens from southern Anatolia and Lebanon); aedeagus as in Figs 68–69.

Remark: The specimens from the type locality and other material collected by J. Frisch are of generally darker colouration in all respects (elytra brown, antennae and legs dark brown). This difference of colouration may be an artefact resulting from the method of preservation.

Comparative notes: This species is distinguished from the similar *B. bedeli* by larger size (*B. bedeli*: body length 3.65–4.40 mm, length of forebody 2.00–2.15 mm), longer antennae with antennomeres VIII–X not (male) or less (female) transverse, and much denser and less coarse punctation of the elytra. As all dissected specimens of *B. bedeli* are females, a comparison of the aedeagi is not possible. Like *B. bedeli*, *B. bedelianus* belongs to the group of species with a membranous posterior emargination of the male sternite VII (see HERMAN 1986).

Distribution and natural history: The species is known from the Greek Southern Sporades (Samos, Rhodos, Karpathos), from central southern Turkey, Lebanon, Israel, and Cyprus. The material from Samos was collected on the banks of streams.

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